

Research Article

Earth's Collective Human Consciousness Focus (CHCF) Serves as the Universe's "Functional Epicenter"!

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Note: Dr. Bentovish is affiliated with Zefat Academic Center (and has been affiliated with Ariel University), and is now seeking one of the leading Physics Universities in the World to further assist him in further direct validation of the New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Scientific Paradigm of 21st Century Theoretical Physics; Dr. Bentovish (Bentwich) e-mail is: drbentovish@gmail.com

Abstract

Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics is undergoing a basic "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM) to the New "G-D's Physics" ("Computational Unified Field Theory", CUFT) Scientific Paradigm! This Paradigmatic Shift follows a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" found in the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm signified by a basic "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM, and its inability to explain the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion (e.g., assumed to be "caused" by purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" which are assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass and energy in the universe, but which could not be detected despite two decades of trying to do so)?! In contrast, the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm has been shown capable of resolving this GRT-QM "theoretical-inconsistency" based on the discovery of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe through an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec"! Based on direct empirical validation of two unique "G-D's Physics" "Critical Predictions", which points at the centrality of a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) in determining the UCP's "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) at the "Jewish Rosh Hashanah" (JRH) two days' special time-interval, a new understanding emerges of this CHCF and associated Earth's localization as the universe's "Functional Epicenter" (e.g., in "space" and "time")! A Call for Astronomers to collaborate with Dr. Bentovish regarding empirical validation of unique "G-D's Physics" "Critical Prediction" associated with this CHCF's Earth's (new) "Functional Epicenter" of the universe is made: drbentovish@gmail.com

Introduction

Twenty-First Century's Theoretical Physics is undergoing a "tantalizing" "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM) to the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm! Perhaps the "principle difference" between the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm and the New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, is the fact that according to the Old Paradigm everything in the universe "occurs" or "functions" strictly based on (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between a "finite" set of "physical" or "material" elements, which occurs "randomly", i.e., with no underlying "purpose", "aim" or "goal"?! In contrast, the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm discovered the existence of a singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec" (!) thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" comprising the entire physical universe at every (consecutive) "minimal time-point"! Therefore, due to the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s), and the complete "dissolution" of the entire physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's

frame/s, according to the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, there cannot exist any "direct" or even "indirect" "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe – at any "single" or "multiple" "Universal Frames"! Moreover, since the only "source" for the "origination", "sustenance", "development" and even "goal" (or "purpose") of all such exhaustive spatial pixels in the entire physical universe (as well as of the whole universe) – is this singular higher-ordered UCP, therefore according to the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm the universe has been "Pre-planned" by this singular UCP in order to attain an "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of the universe, and is (in fact) this singular UCP is continuously "steering" the entire physical universe towards the attainment of this "Ultimate Geulah Goal State" of the universe (and of Humanity) [1-49].

Science (and Humanity) has therefore reached a "pivotal turning point" with the discovery of this New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, which alters (in a very basic and fundamental manner) our basic understanding of the "origin"- "sustenance"- (continuous "dissolution"-) "re-computation" and "development"- of the entire physical universe towards the attainment of that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal

State" of the universe (and of Humanity)! This is because contrary to the basic "material-causal" assumption of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (of GRT & QM), which assumes that the entire physical universe was created by a "random" initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event that "caused" the creation of all the suns, galaxies, planets, energy and mass in the universe; and that the universe is being governed by mere direct (or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between certain "massive objects" and their "curvature of Space-Time" (and conversely that the "travelling-paths" of these "massive" and other "less-massive" objects is determined (or "caused") by this "curved Space-Time"; the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm asserts that there cannot exist any such (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any such "massive" objects and their assumed ("caused") "curvature of Space-Time" – i.e., either in the "same" or "different" UF's frame/s, or "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s, due to the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any such (consecutive) UF's frame/s, and the complete "dissolution" of the entire physical universe back into the singularity of this UCP "in-between" any two such UF's frame/s!

But, before we can appreciate this profound "Paradigmatic-Shift" that is currently taking place in Twenty First Century Theoretical Physics, and its profound theoretical implications regarding the centrality of Earth and the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) as the "functional center" of the whole universe (e.g., in "time", "space" and in terms of fulfilling the UCP's "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State" of Humanity)! We need to describe the preceding "Paradigmatic-Crisis" that characterized the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm; According to Thomas Kuhn's [50], well-accepted analysis of the "Structure of Scientific Revolutions" [50], in order for Science to accept such a "Paradigmatic-Shift" (in any given scientific sub-discipline), it is necessary for a few specific conditions to be fulfilled:

a) The appearance of such a "Paradigmatic-Crisis" (in that given discipline) signified by the existence of a "theoretical-inconsistency" between the "pillars" of the Old ("Material-Causal") Paradigm (e.g., GRT & QM, i.e., as mentioned above), as well as this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's principle inability to explain the accelerated expansion of the physical universe – e.g., assumed to "caused" by purely hypothetical "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts, which are assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the matter in the universe but which could not be detected experimentally despite numerous attempts to do so (despite twenty years of intensive experimentation)?!

b) The ability of the New ("G-D's Physics") Scientific paradigm to resolve this apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT & QM, as well as offer an alternative (satisfactory) theoretical explanation for the accelerated expansion of the universe: Based on "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm's discovery of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle's" (UCP's) simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s), it has been shown that this UCP simultaneously computes all "Single Spatial-Temporal" (SST) "particle/objects"; "Multiple Spatial-Temporal" (MST) "wave-phenomena"; and "Exhaustive Spatial-Temporal" "Universal Frame/s" computations! In this manner, the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm has been shown capable of resolving the apparent "theoretical-inconsistency" between GRT's strict "Speed of Light Barrier" (SLB) as opposed to QM's "Quantum Entanglement" phenomena's implication wherein a certain measurement of one subatomic "entangled particle's" ("complimentary pairs" value may "instantaneously" affect the other "entangled particle's" complimentary (energy/mass or time/mass) value?! This is simply because according to "G-D's Physics broader EST computation – which embeds (within it) the relatively more "constrictive" UCP's MST and SST computations, the apparent "Quantum Entanglement" phenomenon merely represents the UCP's computation of "equivalent SST particle points" along the MST's (subatomic) "wave" computation, which is embedded within

the broader EST UCP's computation! Alongside "G-D's Physics" new (profound) theoretical understanding, wherein the UCP's computation of the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" is based on the UCP's two (out of three) "Computational Dimensions" i.e., "Framework" and "Consistency" four possible combinations: "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), and "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") possible combinations! Hence, "G-D's Physics" new theoretical framework has been shown capable of resolving this apparent "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT's strict SLB's principle constraint imposed upon the transmission of any signal (or even information) across space and time – which seems to be contradicted by Quantum Entanglement's "instantaneous" effect of the measurement of one entangled particle's complimentary pairs' measurement upon the other entangled particle's complimentary value; based on the deeper theoretical understanding of "G-D's Physics" (novel) conceptualization and understanding wherein it is the simultaneous UCP's computation of "equivalent MST wave" "particle-points", coupled with its two "Computational Dimensions" complimentary exhaustive UCP's computation of "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time"), which can account for the apparent "entanglement" of two such "equivalent SST particle points" along the "MST wave" (simultaneous) computation of the UCP's "complimentary-exhaustive" "Frame" – "consistent" ("space") or "inconsistent" ("energy"), or "Object" – "consistent" ("mass") or "inconsistent" ("time") "complimentary pairs"! Likewise, the New "G-D's Physics" theoretical framework offer a new (satisfactory) alternative theoretical explanation for the universe's empirically observed accelerated expansion! This new theoretical explanation of "G-D's Physics" is based on its (novel) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" (CHCFH) which stipulated that whenever there is a large group of individual human-beings all collectively focusing on this singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP), then this brings about an "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCI-ARE), e.g., such as during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashanah" (New Year) two days' special time interval (in which Millions of Jews all over the world collectively focus on this singular UCP) – which was predicted to bring about such an "UNCIARE" increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion!

c) Identification of at least one unique "Critical Prediction" which can differentiate the prediction of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm from the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT & QM: according to Kuhn's50 analysis of the "Structure of Scientific Revolutions", in order for any scientific discipline to accept a basic "Paradigmatic-Shift" from the Old ("Material-Causal") Paradigm to the New ("G-D's Physics") Paradigm it is necessary to identify at least one unique "Critical Prediction" that can differentiate the predictions of the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm from the Old "Material-Causal" GRT's and QM's predictions! Indeed, if at least one such (unique) "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm is verified as "more valid" than the corresponding predictions of the Old Paradigm's GRT's & QM's predictions – then (according to Kuhn's50 well accepted analysis) that particular scientific discipline (e.g., in our case Theoretical Physics) has to accept the New "G-D's Physics" as the New (satisfactory) Physics Paradigm (for the Twenty-First Century)! Indeed, we've been blessed with such an identification of two such (unique) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm – which are being shown to be "more valid" than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM, therefore leading to the unequivocal acceptance of "G-D's Physics" as the New Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century!

Methods & Results

In order to directly contrast between the New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm and the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, "G-d's Physics" identified a unique "Critical-Prediction" stemming from its new "computational definitions" of the four basic physical

features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time" – based on the UCP's singular higher-ordered two "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" (frame/object) and "Consistency" (consistent/inconsistent): According to this new UCP's Computational Dimensions definition of the "mass" of any given particle as an "object-consistent" computational measure:

$$M: \sum \{O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i \dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i \dots n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i \dots n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical):

such that:

$$M: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i \dots n)] \leq n * h \{UF's(i \dots n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceed a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value.

"G-d's Physics" unique "Critical-Prediction" predicts that relatively "more-massive" particles such as the (negatively charged) "Muon" would be measured as more "spatially-consistent" than an equivalently (negatively charged) "electron" particle! This unique "G-d's Physics" "Critical-Prediction" was de-facto tested by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" associated experiments conducted by [54-56].

The "Proton-Radius Puzzle" Confirms "G-D's Physics" Critical Prediction

Pohl et al. [54-56], set to measure the radius of a Hydrogen Proton – contrasting between the Standard Hydrogen surrounded by the (negatively charged) electron, and a "Muonic Hydrogen" in which its electron was replaced by a much more massive (negatively charged) "Muon" particle; Surprisingly, they found that the Proton radius was greatly decreased in the Muonic-Hydrogen, than in the Standard Hydrogen – which they termed as the "Proton-Radius Puzzle", because it could not be satisfactorily accounted for by Relativistic or Quantum Models?!

In contrast, these findings conform and validate the unique "Critical-Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm stemming from its above-mentioned new UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given subatomic particle:

$$M: \sum \{O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i \dots n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i \dots n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i \dots n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical).

This is because according to the New "G-d's Physics" UCP's computational definition of the "mass" value of any given subatomic particle, a more massive a particle possesses more "spatially-consistent" physical features – therefore predicting the "Critical-Prediction" of the relatively "more-massive" Muonic Hydrogen Proton possessing a more "spatially-consistent", i.e., smaller and more accurate, than the relatively "less-massive" electron-associated Standard Hydrogen Proton measurements!

Noteworthy is the fact that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm regarding the more "spatially-consistent" measurements of the relatively more massive "Muon-Hydrogen" as opposed to

the relatively less-massive "electron-Hydrogen" – could not be accounted for by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of RT & QM (e.g., despite various attempts to explain this "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings: the "three-body force" [49], interactions between gravity and the weak force, or a flavour-dependent interaction [53,57], higher dimension gravity [48], a new boson [52], and the quasi-free hypothesis

$\pi+$ [51]; and therefore constitutes a direct empirical validation of this New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm!

The "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG) Confirms "G-D's Physics" "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Another means for testing a unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm relates to the "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE) due to the Collective Human Consciousness Focus (CHCF) associated with the two days' "Rosh-Hashana" time-interval in which Millions of Jews are collectively focusing upon this singular higher-ordered UCR/UCP; In contrast to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts' ensuing "constant-rate" of the universe's expansion acceleration – which should not increase with time! Based on the New "G-D's Physics" "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" which assumes that the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion undergoes a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion", at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" two days' special time-interval! An indirect empirical validation of this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm was already given based on the unexplained findings regarding the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG)!

Empirically, a basic (unexplained) "gap" exists between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion 58-61?! This "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) negates the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumption of the existence of (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts as "causing" the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion; because even if such (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" concepts existed (e.g., which failed to be detected after two decades of experimentation), according to the New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm they could not interact (directly or indirectly) with any constituting element of the universe "causing" it to accelerate the rate of the universe's expansion! Therefore, they could not result in the observed CAAEG "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Therefore, the abovementioned results unequivocally validate and support two unique "Critical Predictions" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM: as indicated by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings, and by the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap"! In this respect (as stated above), we now stand at an equivalent "historic juncture" to Eddington's 1919 Solar Eclipse empirical validation of Einstein's GRT's "Critical Prediction" regarding Mercury's double-valued Perihelion curvature around the Sun – which validated Einstein's GRT as more valid than the Older Newtonian Mechanics Paradigm! This is because the empirical validations of these two (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" indicate that "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is more valid and exhaustive than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying GRT and QM, and in fact includes both of them as "special cases" within the broader, more exhaustive theoretical

framework of "G-D's Physics" newly discovered Universal Computational Formula (UCF) (as outlined above).

Discussion

Based upon the unequivocal support of "G-D's Physics" two (unique) "Critical Predictions" as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT & QM, we reach the inevitable conclusion wherein there exists only one singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe for every consecutive UF's frame/s (e.g., at the "unfathomable" rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec!") thereby creating an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every such "minimal time-point"!

There are a few profound theoretical points stemming from this direct empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation":

A. "G-D's Physics" A-Causal Computation" New Scientific Paradigm:

The acceptance of "G-D's Physics" New (empirically proven) "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm negates the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (e.g., either at the relativistic or quantum subatomic level) existing either in the "same"-of "different" - UF's frame/s, due to the UCP's "simultaneous" computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels for every consecutive UF frame, and the complete "dissolution" of all such exhaustive spatial pixels back into the singularity of this UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Therefore, according to this New (empirically validated) "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, the basic "Big-Bang" Model of GRT is challenged and (in fact) negated (as previously delineated), due to the impossibility of the existence of any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between such a (purely hypothetical) "Big-Bang" nuclear event and the production of any "stars", "planets", "mass" or "energy" etc. – either in the "first", "second", "third"... "trillionth"... "nth" UF's frame/s! Therefore, also the more general Model of GRT's Einstein's Equations, which postulates that for instance, the existence of a purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" or "Dark-Energy" (DM/DE), which alongside the initial "Big-Bang" nuclear explosion created the universe's accelerated expansion rate till this very date – is also strictly negated by "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm! This is because (once again), there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any such (purely hypothetical) DM/DE concepts and the accelerated expansion of the universe – at any single or multiple UF's frame/s! (In fact, as we'll see, there cannot be any "transference" of any physical "effect", "matter", or "phenomenon" etc. – across any series of UF's frame/s, and therefore the only "means" for explaining the continuous "origination", "sustenance" and "development" of the entire physical universe as well as of any exhaustive spatial pixel found within it – may only be explained based on the analysis and deeper understanding of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" which is the sole "reality" underlying and indeed "transcending" the entire physical universe!) So, we reach the inevitable conclusion wherein the universe could not have been "created" or "caused" by any (hypothetical) initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event, because there could not have been any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any such "Big-Bang" nuclear event and its "causing" of the creation of any sun/s, galaxies, mass or energy etc. – in the "first", "second"... "trillionth"... "nth" UF's frame/s (e.g., due to the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe for every consecutive UF's frame/s and the complete "dissolution" of all of these exhaustive spatial pixels back into the UCP's singularity "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s!?) Nor could the universe's accelerated rate of expansion (till this very date!) be attributed to the purely hypothetical DM/DE concepts, once again to the "impossibility" of the existence of

any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any such (purely hypothetical) DM/DE and any of the universe's galactic elements (e.g., assumed to "cause" their "repulsion") at any single- or multiple- UF's frame/s!?

B. The "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) Negates the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's SRCNS Computational Structure:

More fundamentally, one of "G-D's Physics" (profound) newly discovered "Theoretical Postulates", called: the "Computational Duality Principle" has proven (i.e., in principle!) that the basic "Computational Structure" of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm is "flawed", e.g., comprising a "Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS) which was shown to (inevitably) lead to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational-indeterminacy", which are contradicted by these (apparently) SRCS Systems to carry out (successfully) the necessary computation in order to determine the outcome of that System; therefore pointing at the existence of a singular (higher-ordered) UCP, which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (at the "unfathomable" rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec!")

An important computational basis for this New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm are two of its former Theoretical Postulates called: the "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) and associated "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP), which state that it is not possible (in principle) for any two given computational elements ("x") and ("y") to determine (or "cause") the value/s of one of these elements (i.e., "y") – because such a "Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS) would inevitably lead to both a "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational indeterminacy" that are contradicted by that Computational System's proven (empirical) capacity to determine the given 'y' element's values: Specifically in the case of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's (implicitly) assumed "Self-Referential Computational System" "SRCS": it is assumed that it is only based on the direct physical interaction between certain (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter/Dark-Energy" (DMDE) elements and their direct (or even indirect) physical interactions with all (possible) "exhaustive components of the Universe" (Uec) of this SRCS System – that this SRCS System is able to compute whether these "exhaustive components of the Universe" (Uec) would remain the "same" or "different" (e.g., "Not Uec")!

Formally presented, this SRCS System of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm:

SRCS: {DMDE, Uec-aer } → "Uec-aer" or "Not Uec-aer"

But, according to "G-d's Physics" "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) such a SRCS System inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational-indeterminacy" in the case of a "Negative" SRCS outcome, i.e., "SRCNS" – in which this SRCS System yields a "negative outcome":

SRCS: {DMDE, Uec-aer } → "Not Uec-aer"

In which it is assumed that this direct (or indirect) physical interaction between (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter"/"Dark-Energy" (DMDE) concepts and the "exhaustive components of the Universe- accelerated rate of expansion" (Uec) "cause" a "change" in this Uec-aer ("Not Uec-aer"); then this leads to an inevitable "logical-inconsistency" – since this SRCNS System states that the universe possesses both the initial Uec-aer rate of expansion and also possesses a "Not Uec-aer" (increased) rate of expansion! Obviously, such SRCNS "logical-inconsistency" inevitably also leads to an intrinsic state of "computational-indeterminacy" because such a "material-causal" SRCS/SRCNS System cannot determine whether its initial Uec-aer or subsequent Not Uec-aer state of the universe's acceleration rate exists! But, to the extent that we can validate "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion Rate"

(UNCAER) – then this would negate the SRNC assumed computational structure of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm!

Hence, the proposed "Critical-Prediction" of "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm that could differentiate it from the corresponding Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, e.g., regarding the "Big-Bang" Model and associated "Dark-Energy"/"Dark-Matter" should test for "G-d's Physics" predicted "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion Rate" (UNCAER), which coupled with the above CDP would unequivocally validate "G-d's Physics" New ACC Paradigm's conception of the UCP's singular higher-ordered continuous (simultaneous) computation- "dissolution"- re-computation- and evolution of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (for each consecutive UF's frame/s). The results are taken from a series of scientific studies indicating the existence of a significant "gap" between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion (Scolnic et al. 2014; Riess et al. 2018a, 2019; Shajib et al. 2020; Wong et al. 2020)?! As asserted by the abovementioned "G-d's Physics" Computational Duality Principle (CDP), This "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) indicates a SRNCS computational result yielded by the Old "Material-Causal" "Self-Referential Computational Structure" (SRCS):

SRNCS: {DM/DE, Uec-er } ti → {"Not Uec-er"} ti+n

wherein it is assumed that it is the direct (or indirect) physical interaction between (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter"/"Dark-Energy" (DM/DE concepts) and the "exhaustive components of the Universe- expansion rate" (Uec-ar) that "causes" the universe to increase its acceleration rate with time?! But, as the CDP teaches us, such a SRNCS computational state inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency", e.g., an apparent contradiction between the universe's stated expansion rate at ti : as Uec-er; as opposed to its expansion rate as: Not Uec-er at ti+n ?! This "logical-inconsistency" also invariably leads to an associated "computational-indeterminacy" – simply because such assumed SRCS (SRNCS) computational System is unable to decide whether the universe's accelerated rate should be " Uec-er" (at ti) or " Not Uec-er" (at ti+n) ?! But, since according to the CDP we obtain clear empirical results (stated above) wherein the universe in fact exhibits an increase in its acceleration rate over time, e.g., as indicated by the "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG), therefore the CDP asserts that the basic SRCS/SRNCS Computational System assumed by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (of RT & QM) must be negated and rejected! Instead, "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's CDP points at the existence of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/ Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (e.g., at the incredible rate of "c2 /h" = 1.36-50 sec!), thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every consecutive "minimal timepoint"! Indeed, the empirically observed "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) conforms with "G-d's Physics" "Critical Prediction" of the "Universe's Non-Continuous Expansion Accelerated Rate" (UNCEAR) – which is further specified to occur during such (special) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" time-intervals as the "Jewish Rosh-Hashana" (JRH)!

As mentioned above, one of the significant theoretical postulates of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm is called: the "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) which asserts that it is not possible, in principle, to compute any direct (or even indirect) relativistic or quantum physical relationship/s between any given "x" and "y" elements – from within their direct "Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS) assumed computational structure, but only from the higher-ordered singular "Universal Compu-

tational Principle" (UCP); This is because "G-d's Physics" "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) reveals that this "problematic" "Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS) computational structure characterizing the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational-indeterminacy" that are intrinsic to this SRCS computational structure; But, since in all of those Relativistic or Quantum Systems, there exists robust empirical evidence that those Systems are capable of computing the outputted result of the System, therefore the CDP asserts that there must exist a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" computing the various states and existence of these Relativistic or Quantum Systems! The most general representation of this CDP can be given as: Whenever there exists a SRCS System (of the computational structure) assuming that the whole computation is determined solely at the same "di1" computational level:

SRCS: {x, y} → "y" or "Not y"/di1 the possibility of SRNCS (e.g., "negative" "Not y" output): SRNCS {x, y} → "Not y"/di1 Inevitably leads to "logical-inconsistency", since the "y" element seems to both "exist" and "not exist" at the same "di1" computational level?!

SRNCS {x, y} → "Not y"/di1 Such apparent "logical-inconsistency" also inevitably leads to an ensuing "computational indeterminacy", i.e., an apparent inability of such SRCS/SRNCS to determine whether the "y" element exists or "doesn't exist", e.g., denoting a different altered value for this "y" element?! But, since there exists specific empirical evidence for any of these Relativistic or Quantum Systems' capability to determine and output a particular "y" value, therefore this contradicts the Duality Principle's above proof that such an assumed SRCS/ SRNCS Computational System inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational indeterminacy" – therefore the CDP points at the existence of a singular higher-ordered UCP which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (as postulated by "G-d's Physics" "Universal Computational Principle", e.g., thereby producing the extremely rapid series of "Universal-Frames", UF's at the incredible rate of "c2 /h" = 1.36-50 sec! comprising the entire physical universe at every such "minimal timepoint"); Hence, below is a detailing of the various examples and manifestations of this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumed SRCS (& SRNCS) Computational Systems – which are all constrained and in fact negated by "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm, all pointing at the "Computational Duality Principle's" (CDP) asserted singular higher-ordered UCP (of "G-d's Physics New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm)! a). The "Big-Bang Model": The "Big-Bang" Model represents this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumption wherein it is the direct physical interaction/s between a certain "Nuclear Event" (NE) and a given "exhaustive components of the Universe" exhibiting a certain "expansion state" at (U-ec/es) that "causes" the universe's expansion state to "increase", e.g., that is, be "different" than the initial "expansion state", which can be represented as:

SRNCS {NE, (U-ec/es)} → NOT (U-ec/es) /di1

Noteworthy is highlighting the implicit "material-causal" assumption of this "Big-Bang" Model's SRCS/SRNCS Computational System, e.g., whereby this SRCS/SRNCS Computational System assumes that it is solely based on this direct physical interaction between the NE and the initial state of the universe's expansion (U-ec/es) that this SRCS/SRNCS System is able to compute the different NOT (U-ec/es) state of the universe; Specifically that the entire SRCS/SRNCS computation exists at the same "di1" computational level of the SRCS! But, such a SRCS/SRNCS Computational System inevitably leads to a "logical-inconsistency":

SRNCS {NE, (U-ec/es)} → NOT (U-ec/es)/di1?!

This implies that the SRCS/SRNCS Computational System assumed by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm inevitably also leads to an apparent "com-

putational indeterminacy", e.g., an apparent inability of this SRCS/SRNCS Computational System to determine whether the universe will remain its initial (U-ec/e)s state or evolve into the latter "NOT (U-ec/es)"! But, since there exists robust empirical evidence indicating the existence of a significant "gap" between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion (Scolnic et al. 2014; Riess et al. 2018a, 2019; Shajib et al. 2020; Wong et al. 2020) indicates that there exists a Computational System that is capable of determining the universe's accelerated rate of expansion – which actually increases "non-continuously" with time: "NOT (U-ec/es)"! Hence, according to the CDP, this Computational System cannot comprise the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's – but only the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational System" (UCP), which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (e.g., at the incredible rate of "c2/h" = 1.36- 50 sec' of a series of "Universal Frames")! b). General Relativity Theory (GRT) "Einstein's Equations" Another (key) manifestation of this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's basic assumption is GRT's Einstein's Equations basic "material-causal" assumption: According to Einstein's Equations, the presence of certain "Massive Objects" (MO) and their direct physical interaction with "Space-Time" "causes" a change in the curvature level of this "Space-Time": SRNCS {MO, STc} → "NOT STc"/di1 But, once again, such a SRNCS output of the SRCS Computational System basic computational structure inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency", i.e., in intrinsic inability of the SRCS(SRNCS) assumed Computational System to determine whether the initial STc or the subsequent "NOT STc" state of "Space-Time" should exist – since they're both intrinsic elements within the same SRCS/SRNCS "di1" computational level!

SRNCS {MO, STc} → "NOT STc"/di1

Therefore, once again the CDP points at the ensuing "computational-indeterminacy" of such a SRNCS Computational System, which cannot decide whether the resulting state of Relativistic System should remain at the initial STc state or undergo an additional curvature of Space-Time as in the more "curved SpaceTime" state, e.g., signified by "NOT STc"?! But, since the abovementioned clear empirical indication of the existence of a significant "gap" between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion (Scolnic et al. 2014; Riess et al. 2018a, 2019; Shajib et al. 2020; Wong et al. 2020) represents a "special-case" of GRT's Einstein's Equations, then this indicates that the Computational System that is capable of determining the universe's accelerated rate of expansion (associated with Einstein's abovementioned SRCS/SRNCS assumed Computational System); Therefore, once again, the CDP points at the existence of a singular higher-ordered UCP which simultaneously computes every exhaustive spatial pixel's four basic physical features –of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time", giving rise to an extremely rapid series of UF's frames; Indeed, "G-d's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" (ACC) Paradigm was shown to offer an alternative computational account for the apparent "material-causal" "curvature of Space-Time by massive objects" – i.e., based on "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) novel computational definitions of the four basic physical features by this singular higher-ordered UCP, and the new "Universal Computational Formula" which completely unifies (for the first time in Physics) between these four basic physical features of the universe:

S: $(f_i\{x,y,z\}[UF(i)] + \dots f_j\{x,y,z\}[UF(n)]) / h * n \{UF's\}$ such that: $f_j\{x,y,z\}[UF(n)] \leq f_i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\} [UF's(i..n)]$

where the "space" measure of a given object (or event) is computed based on a "Frame-consistent" computation that adds the specific UF's (x,y,z) localization across a series of UF's [i..n] which nevertheless do not exceed the threshold of Planck's constant per each number ("n") of frames (e.g., thereby providing "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's computational definition of "space" as "Frame-consistent" UF's measure! Conversely, the "energy" of any given "object" (e.g., whether it is the spatial dimensions of an object or event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on the event or whether it relates to the spatial location of an object) is computed based on "Frame-inconsistent" differences of a given "object's" location or size across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light ("c") multiplied by the number of UF's across which the "object's" energy value is computed by the UCP:

E: $(f_i\{x,y,z\}[UF(i)] - \dots f_j\{x,y,z\}[UF(n)]) / c * n \{UF's\}$

such that: $f_j\{x,y,z\}[UF(n)] > f_i\{x+(h*n), y+(h*n), z+(h*n)\} [UF's(i..n)]$ wherein the energetic value of a given object, event etc. is computed based on the subtraction of that object's UF's (universal pixels' Coordinate System's location) across a series of UF's, divided by the speed of light multiplied by the number of UF's. In contrast, the computational definition of "mass" of any given "object" is computed by the UCP based on the number of times an "object" is presented "consistently" across a series of UF's, divided by Planck's constant (e.g., representing the minimal degree of inter-frame's changes):

M: $\sum [O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i..n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i..n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i..n)\}$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical): such that:

M: $[O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i..n)] \leq n * h \{UF's(i..n)\}$

Wherein the UCP's computational measure of "mass" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by Planck's constant value. In contrast, the UCP's computational measure of the "time" value is based on the number of instances that a given object has "changed" – relative to the speed of light in terms of its "Object-inconsistent" "internal" {o-x,o-y,o-z} values, across a given series of UF's frames changes:

T: $\sum [O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] \neq O(i..n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i..n)\} / c * n\{UF's(i..n)\}$

such that:

T: $[O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i..n)] \leq c * h \{UF's(i..n)\}$

Wherein the "temporal" value of any given UCP's computational measure of "time" represents its computation of the number of UF's frame/s in which the "Object-consistent" internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF's frames by the speed of light. Universal Computational Formula (UCF): c). Quantum Mechanics "Material-Causal" Assumed Collapse of the Target's Probability Wave-Function: Another important manifestation of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's basic assumption which is challenged and negated by "G-d's Physics" New "Computational Duality Principle" is Quantum Mechanics' "material-causal" assumption wherein it is the direct physical interaction between a given subatomic "probe" (P) element and a corresponding subatomic ("un-collapsed") "target's probability wave-function"

(Tu-wf) – which is assumed to "cause" the "collapse of the probability wave-function" into a single "complimentary" (space/energy or time/mass) value:

$$\text{SRNCS: } \{P, \text{Tu-wf}\} \rightarrow \text{"NOT Tu-wf"}/d1$$

But, as stated above, according to the CDP such a SRNCS Computational System inevitably leads to "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational-indeterminacy":

$$\text{SRNCS: } \{P, \text{Tu-wf}\} \rightarrow \text{"NOT Tu-wf"}/d1$$

Wherein this assumed SRNCS Computational System cannot decide whether the target element should exhibit its assumed "un-collapsed" probability wave function values or the single "complimentary" (space/energy or mass/time) "collapsed" value?! However, since we know empirically that any such QM System is capable of determining the "collapsed" single complimentary value of any given subatomic target element – therefore the CDP points at the existence of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe as an extremely rapid series of Universal Frames (UF's) at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ". As outlined and delineated extensively (previously) the New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm expands, embeds and transcends the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's conception of QM's "single spatial-temporal" "particle", "multiple spatial-temporal" "wave" – and "exhaustive" "Universal Frames" (UF's) computational perspectives which are all embedded within the UCP's singular higher-ordered (integrated) "Universal Computational Formula" (outlined above).

C. The UCP's SST, MST & EST Resolves the "Gravitational Enigma"!

Significantly, "G-D's Physics" discovery of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP), which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe, through its "extremely rapid" (" $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ") computation of the series of "Universal Frame/s" was also shown capable of resolving the basic "unresolved" "Gravitational Enigma" that is associated with "G-D's Physics" complete unification between GRT & QM!

Perhaps the key unresolved "enigma" in Twenty-First Century's Theoretical Physics is the "Gravitational Enigma" (GE), i.e.: Deciphering the underlying mechanism responsible for the phenomenon of "gravitation" which can: a) Unify between General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM); and b) Offer an alternative satisfactory explanation for the universe's accelerated rate of expansion that is not based on the purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" (DM) concept (which is assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe but could not be detected even after two full decades of intensive experimentation?!); c) Unify between the Gravitational Force and the other Three Forces (e.g., Strong- & Weak- Nuclear Forces and the Electromagnetic Force!); d) Offer an alternative theoretical explanation for the "curvature of Space-Time" by "massive objects" (e.g., based on the G-D'S PHYSICS' New Scientific "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm); Thus far, the "Gravitational Force" has been explained based on GRT's key assumption wherein this "Gravitational Force" (GF) is responsible for the "curvature of Space-Time" – i.e., without actually explaining its underlying "nature". Moreover, this assumed GF remains "inexplicable" (and "independent") of the Standard Model's proven capacity to unify between those other Three Forces, based on the discovery of elementary subatomic particles' interactions, and therefore is seen an unresolved "Gravitational Enigma"?! The purpose of this article is to try and offer an alternative solution for this "Gravitational Enigma" (GE) based on the discovery of a New "G-d's Physics" Scientific Paradigm1-30; The potential capacity of this New G-D'S PHYSICS Scientific Paradigm to resolve this "Gravitational Enigma" (GE) stems from its discovery of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the uni-

verse (e.g., at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ "), thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every "minimal time-point"! Additionally, the UCP's simultaneous computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel (in the universe) across a series of (such) UF's frame/s yields the UCP's novel "computational definitions" of the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" (for each exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe) – as being computed by this singular UCP, based on its two "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" and "Consistency! According to this (new) G-D'S PHYSICS explanation, the UCP (simultaneously) computes these four basic physical features – including the "mass" value of each exhaustive spatial pixel (in the universe) based on the four possible combinations of those "Framework" (e.g., "frame" or "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" or "inconsistent") "Computational Dimensions": Such that the UCP computes "Framework" – "consistent" vs. "inconsistent" computations, as the "space" and "energy" values of any given spatial pixel (across a given series of UF's); and "Object" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" computations, as the "mass" and "time" values (across a given UF's series) (Figure 1):

FIGURE 1: UCP'S COMPUTATION OF FOUR PHYSICAL FEATURES

Framework/Consist.	Frame	Object
Consistent	"Space"	"Mass"
Inconsistent	"Energy"	"Time"

Intriguingly, these novel "G-D'S PHYSICS" UCP's "computational definitions" of the four basic physical features also led to the discovery of an "Universal Computational Formula" (Figure 2), which was shown to completely integrate these four basic physical features as secondary computational "by-products" of this singular (higher-ordered) UCP (for the first time in Physics)!

FIGURE 2: The "UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA" (UCF)

$$\left. \begin{array}{c} c^2 \\ h \end{array} \right\} = \frac{s * e}{t * m}$$

UF's {n...n...x} [Px] (a...z)

Note: which is accompanied by "G-D'S PHYSICS" computational (above) definitions of these four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time".

The UCF's Relativistic Format:

$$\left. \begin{array}{c} E * s \\ t \end{array} \right\} = \left. \begin{array}{c} M * c^2 \\ h \end{array} \right\}$$

in which GRT's (famous) "Energy-Mass Equivalence" is embedded within the UCF.

The UCF's Quantum Format:

$$\left. \begin{array}{c} t * m = h * \\ s * e \quad c^2 \end{array} \right\}$$

in which "Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle's" ("complimentary pairs") are embedded as "special cases" within the UCF (see previously elaborated analysis of "G-D'S PHYSICS" or G-D'S PHYSICS).

Significantly, the first (abovementioned) facet of this New G-D'S PHYSICS Scientific Paradigm's potential resolution of the GE's first component – i.e., a) Deciphering the underlying mechanism responsible for the phenomenon of "gravitation" which can both unify between General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM); is given through this (singular higher-ordered) UCP's (in-depth) analysis of the (true) "computational basis" of the "theoretical-inconsistency" between GRT & QM stems: According to the New G-D'S PHYSICS's computational analysis, this "GRT-QM theoretical inconsistency" stems from GRT's strict "Speed of Light Barrier" for the transmission of any "signal" (or even "information") across "space" and "time" – which seems to be "contradicted" by QM's "Quantum Entanglement Phenomenon", indicating that the measurement of one "entangled particle" "instantaneously" affects the "complimentary" ("space/energy" or "mass/time") measurement of the other "entangled particle"?! But, according to the new CUT's Paradigm, the (alternative) explanation and "resolution"- of this apparent "GRT-QM theoretical inconsistency" stems from the UCP's singular (higher-ordered simultaneous) computation of all "Single Spatial-Temporal" computation ("SST"): "particle" of relativistic "object" (e.g., relating to only "one" spatial-temporal point, at any given moment), "Multi Spatial-Temporal" computation (MST): "wave" (e.g., relating to at least "two" points being measured at any point in time) or "Exhaustive Spatial Temporal" (EST) computation (e.g., relating to all "exhaustive" spatial pixels comprising an entire "Universal Frame", UF), across a series of UF's frames (Figure 3);

FIGURE 3: UCP'S "SST", "MST" & "EST" COMPUTATIONS

UCP's Computations	SST	MST	EST
Num. "ST" Points	1	2+	All Points

In order to advance towards demonstrating in what manner can this New G-D'S PHYSICS Scientific Paradigm address and resolve the "second" (abovementioned) facet of the GE, we must now validate a unique "Critical Prediction" of this New G-D'S PHYSICS – as "more valid" than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying GRT & QM!

D. "G-D's Physics" Novel "Universal Computational Formula" (UCF) Complete Unification Between GRT & QM!

E. "G-D's Physics" "Computational Invariance Postulate" & "Universal Consciousness Reality" Postulates

The next (profound) realization of "G-D's Physics" regarding the true nature of the physical universe is brought about through two additional (unique) Theoretical Postulates, namely: the "Computational Invariance

Principle" and the "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR)

F. The UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions & UCF!

A Brief Summary of "G-D's Physics" Theoretical Postulates is outlined (in order to provide an exhaustive summary of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm):

a) The UCP's Three Computational Dimensions:

Indeed, the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm offers a new (and exciting) theoretical explanation for the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP simultaneously computes the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" – based on two out of its three hypothesized "Computational Dimensions", e.g., "Framework" ("frame" vs. "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" vs. "inconsistent"); According to "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm, the UCP simultaneously computes for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire physical universe these four basic physical features based on particular computational combinations, e.g., an "Object" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" computation derives the two (corresponding) physical features of "mass" and "time", whereas the UCP's computation of any given object's "Frame" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" values yields its "space" and "energy" characteristics!

b) The Universal Consciousness Reality's (UCR) "Ten-Hierarchical Computational Dimensions":

1) The UCR's "Wisdom/Free-Will" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("חכמה"):

The UCP's first (initial highest) Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the UCP's "Wisdom/Free-Will" which relates to the UCP's complete "Free-Will" in its computation and "laws" pertaining to the successive computation- "dissolution" re-computation- and evolution- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (e.g., since it is not bound by any "material-causal" physical interactions and it possesses Infinite Wisdom); Indeed, this initial UCR's "Free-Will/Wisdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension is characterized by a "Free-Will/Wisdom" of the UCR's initial conception of the creation of an apparently "separate" and "independent" physical universe – which seems to exist "independently" of the UCR's sole creation, sustenance and evolution of it(!?), but which will nevertheless evolve into the ultimate "Goal" of creating Human-Beings possessing the most "expansive" form of Consciousness that will recognize and appreciate the sole existence and "All-Goodwill" characteristics of this singular higher-ordered UCR! It represents the UCP's initial impetus and Wisdom's conception of the possibility of creating an apparently "independent" physical universe (e.g., from its true sole "Universal Consciousness Reality's" sustenance of it) that will "evolve" the most "expansive" form of Human Consciousness leading to a recognition and appreciation of the singularity of this UCR's "Infinite Wisdom", "All-Goodness" characteristics!

2) The UCP's "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension ("בינה"):

The UCP's secondary Hierarchical Computational Dimension of "All-Goodness/Computation" (בינה) regards the further development of the UCR's "Hierarchical Computational Plan" execution of this initial "Free-Will/Wisdom" general conception of the creation of an apparently "independent" physical universe that evolves into Humanity's ultimate "Geulah " State of recognizing, appreciating and living in accordance with this singular UCR's "All-Goodness" characteristics: This secondary "All-Goodness/Computation" Hierarchical Dimension conceives of the UCP's principle computation of each and every exhaustive spatial pixel – possessing the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time", which allows for the creation of apparently "independent" "living-organisms", e.g., each possessing varying degrees of "awareness" or "Consciousness", and existing apparently "independent" of their true-sole- source of the Universal Consciousness Reality!?! Indeed, it is this apparent "independence" of every Biological form (e.g., plants, animals

and human-beings) from the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which manifests the UCR's "All-Goodness" benevolent characteristic, since it sustains all of Life – continuously creating- "dissolving"- re-creating- and evolving every living form throughout its life-cycle, as well as produces ever more "expansive" form of Consciousness (e.g., leading up to human-beings, as further delineated in the third Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below):

3) The UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/ דעת).

The UCR's fourth Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the "Reversed-Time 'Geulah ' Goal" which describes (for the first time in the UCR's successive hierarchical manifestation of the physical universe) the UCR's full-complete "Blueprint Architectural Hierarchical Plan" for creating and "evolving" the entire physical universe in order to create- progressively more "expansive" forms of Consciousness, i.e., from "inanimate", "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the "Ultimate Geulah Goal" of Humanity's (and Science's) recognition of the sole and singular reality of the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR); It describes the UCR's entire Hierarchical Computational Plan for evolving and manifesting increasingly more "expansive" forms of this singular UCR – e.g., from inanimate "matter", through "animate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to the most "expansive" form of "Collective Human Consciousness" recognizing and leading a "Perfected: Moral, Spiritual & Physical State": in which Humanity recognizes the singularity of this "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) including the basic, "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which compels human-beings and Humanity as a whole to lead a Moral, Harmonious & Peaceful Human Existence. It is termed "Daat" (דעת) in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah tradition because it signifies the UCR's "Knowledge" or "Plan" for the entire evolution of the physical universe – leading to the UCR's "Ultimate Geulah Goal"! Indeed, this fourth Hierarchical Computational "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension offers a new profound insight into the UCR's overall "pre-planned successive evolution" of the entire physical universe – "conceived" of and "pre-planned" from the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" in a "reversed direction" through all "past" - "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" (based on every Individual Human Consciousness' Moral Choice/s made at each point in time, as will be described in the "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension)! Just as an Architect constructing a complex and elaborate building will pre-plan all of the details of this complex and beautiful building in an Architectural "Blueprint", e.g., including all of the details regarding the necessary "construction-steps" to attain the desired "end-goal" of the full Elaborate Complex Building, so it is suggested the UCR also "pre-planned" all of the necessary "past", "present" and (multiple possible) "future/s" of all the Universal Frames depicting the evolution of the entire physical universe in order to evolve the progressive ("inanimate" and "animate": plants, animals and human-beings) forms of Consciousness leading to the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" of Humanity (and Science)! Hence, the fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Daat"/ דעת) signifies the UCR's complete "Knowledge" or "Plan" for evolving the entire physical universe – from inanimate matter through animate: plants, animals and human-beings towards the Perfected "Geulah Goal State", and it is computed and "corrected" to reach this Perfected "Geulah -State" through a continuous "adjustment" process of the UCR based on its later "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" and closely associated "UCR's Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" (as listed below).

4) The fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Chessed"/ חסד):

this "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" relates to the actual execution of the UCR's fourth "Reversed-Time Geulah -Goal" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, i.e., based on a Compassionate ("Chessed/חסד") Moral Principle which allows every human-being to "correct" any of his or

her "Immoral Action/s" through the UCR's computation of an equivalent "future" corresponding to any such "immoral action", which would allow that "offending human-being" to experience the same kind (and degree) of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon another Individual Human-Being, so that the "offending" person could make a sincere "Teshuva" (termed so in the Jewish Tradition) signifying a sincere remorse and accompanying conscious choice not to repeat any such "immoral-action/s" in the future! Since we've seen that the whole Goal of the UCR's evolution of the entire physical universe is solely towards reaching that "Perfected Geulah State" in which all human-beings (and Humanity more generally) would recognize the Oneness, Morality and Peace characterizing the singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) and lead a Moral, Peaceful and Harmonious life, therefore the means for reaching this end Goal of "Geulah " may be attained through the (fourth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Dimension – which produces a "moral correction-mechanism" allowing every individual human-being (and Humanity as a whole) to "perfect" its moral behavior and awareness this through this "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle"! A "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized which tries to demonstrate the "correction-dynamics" of this UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium mechanism: A scenario in which a Trampoline Sheath is placed with a "Metal-Bar" connecting two particular "points" on its surface, such that when one of these particular "point" "decides" to "inflict-pain/suffering" upon the other "point" by pressing the "Metal-Bar" against that other point, we realize that "automatically" the "suffering point" will "push-back" the same "Metal-Bar" against the initially "aggressive-point" to "balance" the Trampoline-Sheath back to its original "resting state"... This "Trampoline Metaphor" has been utilized to explain the "UCR's Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" which constantly and continuously strives to restore the "Oneness", "Peace" and "Harmony" characterizing the UCR's basic nature, e.g., to "correct" for any "moral-imbalance" created by any single one Individual Human Consciousness (person) deciding any "immoral-choice" against another given individual which brings about a "balancing-act" of the UCR creating an equivalent situation in which that "inflicting-pain/suffering" individual would have to experience him/herself the same degree and kind of pain/suffering that he/she inflicted upon the other individual, in order to realize the "inseparability" and "Oneness" of the UCR underlying both Human Consciousness...

5) The Fifth UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Devorah"/ נבורה):

denotes the UCR's actual translation of the fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" into a computation of all "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each Individual human-being for every moral choice that he/she makes at any given point in time! In other words, the UCR simultaneously computes for all human-beings in the world one of multiple possible "future/s" based on each of these individual human-beings' "moral/immoral choice/s", geared towards executing the above mentioned "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" on order to "teach" or "correct" each individual human-being's moral choice/s and realization of the underlying singular "Oneness" of the UCR comprising all individual human beings and more generally the entire physical universe (including all of its "inanimate" and "animate" forms); This steers Humanity and the entire world towards the realization of the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State aimed for by the singular higher-ordered UCR reality!

6) The UCR's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Tiferet"/ תפארת):

the sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" Hierarchical Computational Dimension postulates that the actual manifestation of the entire physical universe critically depends upon the UCR's close relationship with a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" aimed towards that UCR! In other words, according to "G-d's Physics" New 21st century Paradigm, the UCR's actual computation of all past- present and "multiple possible future/s" Universal Frames (UF's) constituting each consec-

utive Year's (time-frame) critically depends upon the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus", in which Millions of individual human-beings simultaneously focus on this singular higher-ordered UCR during a "special time-interval", i.e., such as at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" New Year two-days' time-interval in which Millions of Jews focus collectively upon this singular higher-ordered UCR! This sixth Hierarchical Computational "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" instigates the UCR's computation of an entire New Year derived from the (fifth) UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" – allowing for the entire physical universe development for an entire New Year, based on the already determined "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" for each individual human-being for the entire New Year! One of the direct empirical ramifications of this sixth "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Computational Dimension" correlated with one of the (two) unique "Critical-Predictions" differentiating the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm from the corresponding predictions of both Relativity Theory and Quantum Mechanics, i.e., relating to "G-d's Physics" prediction that during the "special-time" of such a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" taking place every Jewish New-Year's "Rosh-Hashana" two days interval (e.g., this year occurring at : Sep. 7th & 8th , 2021) there will be a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion" of the entire physical universe! This is due to "Collective Human Consciousness Focus (sixth) Hierarchical Computational Dimension's assertion wherein such a 'Collective Human Consciousness Focus', wherein Millions of Jews (all around the world) collectively focus on- and pray towards- this singular higher-ordered UCR, which is assumed to bring about the UCR's computation of all of the "past", "present" and "multiple possible future/s" UF's for all individual human beings – as well as the accelerated new expansion rate for the entire physical universe for the subsequent New Jewish Year! Alongside the previous (third) "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension's" realization that the UCR "pre-plans" the entire evolution of the universe including its evolution from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings all leading towards the Ultimate "Geulah Goal" of Human Moral and Spiritual Perfection and recognition of the singularity and "All-Goodness" nature of this UCR, we can understand that the UCR opts to compute an entire "New (Jewish) Year" in response to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hierarchical Dimension – which manifests also in the "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion of the Universe" during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" two days' special "Collective Human Consciousness Focus"! Obviously, as will be elaborated below, to the extent that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm will be validated empirically, then this will lead to the acceptance of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm as the New Paradigm for 21st century Theoretical Physics, since it negates the existence of "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" and significantly differs from the corresponding predictions of both RT & QM, representing the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of 20th century Physics! The Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah symbol given to this sixth "Collective Human Consciousness Hierarchical Computational Dimension" is "תפארת/Tiferet" which translates as "Glorification" because it signifies such "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Glorification-or focus on- and prayer towards- this singular, higher-ordered UCR.

7) The Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("Netzach"/"Eternal"):

signifies the UCR's actual simultaneous computation of all of the two "Object – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) values for all objects comprising the entire physical universe for each single UF frame, based on all of the previous (above mentioned) Hierarchical Computational Dimensions; it represents the beginning of the actual manifestation of any single UF's frame portrayal of the entire physical universe, which fulfills and advances the UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal" Dimension, and furthers the "UCR's Collective Human Consciousness Focus" computation of an entire New Year's ("past", "present" and "multiple future/s") UF's frames – now being executed for each single UF's frame's constitution of

all comprising object's (mass and time) values! It is also represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah symbol of "נצח" "Eternal" or "Victory" because the UCR's actual computation of any single UF frame's comprising Object's (mass and time) values all constituting objects indeed signifies the advancement of the UCR's "Reversed Time Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension", which represents the "Eternal" or Ultimate "Geulah -State" of the world.

8) The "Teshuva"("תשובה")/"הוד"/"Hod"/"Forgiveness" Eighth Hierarchical Computational Dimension:

Signifies the UCR's allowance for a "Teshuva"/ "repentance" of every individual human-being prior to the actual execution of the seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal" – wherein if any individual person chooses to ask "forgiveness" from the other person upon which it inflicted pain or suffering as well as from the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR) and makes a conscious resolute decision to not repeat any such wrongdoing moral action/s (which constitutes the Jewish term of "Teshuva"); in such case, the UCR's Eighth "Teshuva" Hierarchical Computational Dimension will re-compute and in fact alter the already selected Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal") values computed for that individual human-being's computed immediate pending "future" UF, i.e., replacing the "correcting" equivalent UF frame in which this "offending" individual would have to experience an "equivalent" painful experience (to the one experienced by the person offended by the "immoral choice" made by him/her) with a "positive" immediate future UF frame – based on the fact that that individual human-being already made "Teshuva" (sincere repentance and resolute decision not to repeat any such "immoral" action/s!) It is represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah term of "הוד"/"Hod" which can be translated as "Magnanimity" because it portrays the UCR's magnanimous "forgiveness" capacity to allow for any individual human-being to make a sincere "Teshuva", thereby altering the whole evolution of the universe, based on the "corrected" moral choices of all of its individual human-beings; Indeed, it is a magnanimous UCR that allows for Humanity's "partnership" and "active role" in advancing its Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" State, at every point in time...

9) The Ninth UCR's "Actual Computed Object Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("יסוד"/"Yesod" (Foundation)):

Signifies the UCR's actually computed values for all of the objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s which is based on all previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions! It is therefore represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah term of "יסוד"/"Yessod" or "Foundation" the UCR's actual computed Object (mass/time) values of all constituting objects in the universe for each consecutive UF's frame! Note, however, that this "יסוד"/"Foundation" Ninth Hierarchical Computational Dimension does not (yet) contain the two other essential UCP's "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features which are necessary to execute and actual UF's frame of the universe at any minimal time-point, which is computed by the Tenth Hierarchical Computational Dimension; This also correlates to the fact that the UCR's integral and essential (forth) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle's" Hierarchical Computational Dimension's "moral-balancing" characteristic of the UCR's continuous and constant advancement of the universe (and Humanity) towards the Ultimate "Geulah -Goal" Perfected Moral and Spiritual State necessarily involves the UCR's computation of "pairs" of "offending-offended" individual human-beings, which would have to experience the equivalent "corrected" Moral State, e.g., involving their "placement" within the same UF's frame/s (once again, computed by the UCR's Tenth "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Kingdom" Hierarchical Computational Dimension, below:)

10) The "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computa-

Universal Formula"/"מלכות"/"Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כתר"/"Keter-Infinitude ("Crown")):

This tenth concluding Hierarchical Computational Dimension signifies the UCR's actual computation of each consecutive Universal Frame (UF), including all of its four basic physical features of "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time), and "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) for every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising the entire universe (for each minimal time-point UF's frame/s)! It consumes all of the previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions as comprising any single consecutive UF's frame/s, thereby executing and "building" the "Kingdom" of the UCR's series of UF's inevitably leading to Its "Ultimate Geulah -Goal" Perfected State of the world and the universe! This includes the full integration of the previous (ninth) "יסוד"/"Yessod"- "Foundation" Hierarchical Computational Dimension' comprising only the two "Object" – "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time) physical features associated with every exhaustive object comprising the entire physical universe, together with the two other "Frame" – "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) physical features that are necessary in order to create any single (consecutive) UF's frame! It also necessitates the direct involvement and

"power" of the Infinite UCR's Essence (or "כתר" / "Crown") as it is called in the Jewish Chassidic-Kabballah Tradition which (as it were) "stands alone" in its infinitude – beyond the four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time", i.e., Prior to its manifesting of the entire physical universe through its associated "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions"! Indeed, as can be glanced from this "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" (below), the direct "involvement" of this "כתר"/"Keter" – Infinitude ("Crown") Essence of the UCR is seen both "prior to" and "above" the UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions ("standing alone" as the "כתר"/"Keter"-Crown" of these Ten Dimensions) and is also apparent in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions Universal Computational Formula" – in the "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension (" כתר"/"Keter-Infinitude ("Crown")); This is because in order to manifest, integrate and compute the entire physical universe simultaneously – at the incredible rate of " c^2/h " = 1.36^{50} (sec') for each exhaustive spatial pixel it necessitates the Infinite Wisdom and Essence of the UCR!

Figure 4: THE TEN HIERARCHICAL DIMENSIONS' UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA (THD-UCF):

FIGURE 5: The "UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" Diagram

G-D's Physics" Centrality of the Earth's Collective Human Consciousness Focus" in the Universe!

The Centrality of "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) in "G-D's Physics" New Universe!

One of the key differences between the New (empirically validated) "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm and the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm is the "Centrality of Human Consciousness" – i.e., in "space" and "time", and its intimate connection with the "Universal Consciousness Reality's" (UCR's) "Geulah Driven Universe" (GDU)! This is because according to "G-D's Physics" New (empirically proven) Scientific Paradigm, it seems that "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) plays a major role in the "Universe's Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE)! As we've already seen, there is clear (and direct) empirical evidence for the centrality of this CHCF in terms of its UNCIARE's acceleration in the universe! As outlined above, in contrast to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" concept (e.g., which has been negated both based on the experimental failure to detect its existence experimentally, and "G-D's Physics" principle computational negation of its associated Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's SRCS Computational Structure!) – which assumes that this (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" concept can only account for a "constant-rate" expansion rate of the universe; the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm points at an increase in the rate of the universe's expansion, e.g., "UNCIARE" due to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus", which occurs during the Jewish Rosh Hashanah's (two days' special) time-interval!

Indeed, it has been proven empirically (above) that it is solely based on this CHCF that the universe's rate of expansion **increases over time**, e.g., as indicated by the (otherwise unexplained) "Universe's Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UCAGUARE)!; An even more direct (further) validation of the centrality of the CHCF was called for Astronomers to validate during the upcoming two days' Jewish Rosh Hashanah – during September 16th & 17th 2023, in which it is predicted that the universe's rate of expansion will significantly increase (and continue to increase) during the whole ensuing Jewish year, relative to the universe's measured rate of expansion in the preceding time prior to Sep. 16-17th! Moreover, previously it's been shown that this same CHCF may be responsible for the Centrality of Human Consciousness – not just in "time" but also in "space"! This relates to the otherwise "unexplained" empirically validated phenomenon wherein the Astronomical measurement of the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion (UARE) also indicates that planet Earth stands at the center of this UARE! In other words, it may be the case wherein the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion – i.e., related to "space", wherein it is only relative to planet Earth's position that this accelerated rate of expansion pertaining to the furthest regions of space (wherein the farther any galactic element exists relative to planet Earth the faster its measured acceleration would be)! If (for instance) it is found that such equivalent Astronomical measurements of the UARE – do not yield the same "symmetrical increase" in the universe's UARE then this would validate the centrality of planet Earth (and its associated centrality of this CHCF) – in "space", as well as in "time"!

"G-D's Physics" Novel CHCF's Center of the Universe Hypothesis!

We therefore reach an "astonishing" new Hypothesis of "G-D's Physics", i.e., hypothesizing that at the center of the universe's existence, dynamics and development – stand our planet Earth due to this CHCF, including the rotation of our sun (around it) and the accelerated expansion of other galactic elements "emanating" from planet Earth's CHCF! This is because once we realize that the evolution of the physical universe cannot be explained merely due to an any initially assumed "Big-Bang" nuclear event- e.g., based on the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm (above); and that (in fact), the basic SRCS Computational Structure of the Old "Material-Causal"

Paradigm was shown to be negated by "G-D's Physics" (novel) "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) – i.e., as inevitably leading to both "logical-inconsistency" and (ensuing) "computational indeterminacy" that are both negated by the CDP's insistence upon the (proven) capacity of this apparently negated SRCS Computational System to determine the accelerated expansion of the universe – which (according to the CDP) points at the singularity of this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) as simultaneously computing all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s)! And most significantly, empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" (above) unique "Critical Prediction" regarding the "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) – as more valid than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's assumed "constant rate" of the universe's expansion rate! Therefore, we must negate (and reject) the Old "Material-Causal" GRT's Paradigm's assumption wherein the entire physical universe has been created (or "caused") by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event, and that its accelerated rate of expansion can be explained through the (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" concept (which has been negated based on the three abovementioned considerations)!

The alternative (novel) explanation offered by the New (empirically validated) "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm for the origination- sustenance- and development- of the whole physical universe is solely based on the operation of the singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) that (solely) exists both "during" its computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s (as solely responsible for the computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel's four basic physical features of "space", "energy", "mass" and "time"!); And specifically, as associated with this UCP's connection with the CHCF – which brings about the UCP's initiation of the UNCIARE (empirically validated) phenomenon! In other words, the UNCIARE empirically validated phenomenon (unequivocally) proves that the origination of the entire physical universe, and its accelerated rate of expansion (e.g., as indicated by the "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion", CAGUARE) is brought about by the UCP's consecutive computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s – and specifically by the CHCF's UNCIARE increase in the rate of the universe's expansion, e.g., assumed to take place at every Annual "Jewish Rosh-Hashanah" two days' time-interval (i.e., this year this will take place during Sep. 16-17th 2023 and onwards in which it is predicted the rate of the universe's expansion will increase significantly, relative to the rate of the universe's expansion prior to the 16-17th – which I've called Astronomers and Cosmologists to test experimentally!) Indeed, once we realize that the entire physical universe "dissolves" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s and that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in any single- or multiple- UF's frame/s; and therefore that the only "force" that creates- "dissolves"- re-creates- and evolves- any exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe is this singular higher-ordered UCP; hence, based on the clear empirical evidence indicating an UNCIARE increase in the rate of the universe's expansion associated with the CHCF (hypothesized to take place during the Jew Rosh Hashanah!) we reach the inevitable theoretical conclusion wherein the expansion of the entire physical universe depends upon the CHCF – which brings about this UNCIARE increase in the universe's expansion rate (beginning in each Jewish Rosh Hashanah and continuing throughout the entire subsequent Jewish Year).

We therefore reach the inevitable conclusion wherein taking together these two empirically validated facts:

a) Empirical Validation of "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE (annual) increase in the rate of the universe's expansion, which according to G-D's Physics is associated with the CHCF (e.g., specifically during the Jewish "Rosh-Hashanah" special two days' time interval, as noted above: a call for Astrono-

mers/Cosmologists to test this UNCIARE-JRH during the upcoming Sep. 16th-17th, 2023 & onwards!) In other words, this UNCIARE (JRH) empirically confirmed phenomenon points at the centrality of CHFC “in time”, i.e., specifically during the JRH (e.g., to be directly confirmed through the above call for Astronomers/Cosmologists to test during the upcoming JRH!)

b) Centrality of Earth's CHCF for the Universe's Observed Accelerated Rate of Expansion! The empirically observed “unexplained” “Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion” CAGUARE (indicates that the rate of the universe's expansion has increased (significantly) from its early “Background Radiation” stage to the current (increased) rate in the universe's expansion! This phenomenon is associated with Planet Earth's “Epicenter” of the universe – in “space” (e.g., based on the fact that the accelerated rate of our regions of the universe is proportional to the distance from “Earth”!)

Taken together, these empirically validated (major otherwise “unexplained”) phenomena point at the centrality of Earth's “Collective Human Consciousness Focus” – in “space” and “time”: as the (functional) center of the universe! It also reinforces the singularity of the higher-ordered “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” as the sole source “originating” the entire physical universe (at the incredible rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ (sec⁻¹)!

Indeed, over and beyond the abovementioned empirical validations of “G-D's Physics” two unique “Critical Predictions”, e.g., associated with the “UNCIARE” and “Proton-Radius Puzzle” findings, the two above empirical findings, i.e., regarding: a) Empirical Validation of “G-D's Physics” UNCIARE (annual) increase in the rate of the universe's expansion, which according to G-D's Physics is associated with the CHCF; b) Centrality of Earth's CHCF for the Universe's Observed Accelerated Rate of Expansion! clearly point at the Earth's CHCF's associated “Epicenter of the Universe” – i.e., both in “time” & “space”! Once again, if we wish to further validate in an even more direct manner the centrality of “Earth's Epicenter of the Universe” (EEU) related to its CHCF (EEU-CHCF), then Astronomers are invited to test two additional unique “Critical Predictions” of “G-D's Physics” New Scientific Paradigm:

1) UNCIARE-JRH: as noted (above), an even more direct empirical validation of “G-D's Physics” “A-Causal Computation” New Scientific Paradigm, relates to a further testing of its additional “Critical Prediction” regarding the UNCIARE at the (upcoming) JRH (Sep. 16-17th 2023) in which it is predicted that the rate of the universe's expansion will increase during these two days (and continue constantly throughout the next Jewish Year, relative to the rate of the universe's expansion rate prior to Sep. 16-17th)!

2) EEU Validation: “Non-Earth's Non-Epicenter Measurements” (NEN-EM)! An additional (even more direct) testing of the Centrality of Earth's CHCF for the Universe's Observed Accelerated Rate of Expansion would be an empirical validation of a measurement of the universe's “non-harmonious”, i.e., “non-equivalent” accelerated expansion rate – of the farthest regions of the universe, when measured at a location “distant” from Earth (e.g., such as for instance from “Mars” or other “distant” Non-Earth location)! This is because, if indeed, any such measurement of the universe's accelerated rate of expansion (of a greater rate of expansion proportional to the distance from Earth's measurement) would be found to be “un-equivalent” (in all directions – for all furthest regions of the universe), as opposed to the accelerated (“equivalent” or “harmonious”) rate of the universe's expansion as measured from “Earth's Universe's Epi-center” (EEU), then this would indicate that indeed Earth's (CHCF) Epicenter is in fact that the (functional) center of the entire physical universe!

In order to be able to accept this new (profound) metamorphosis of the

Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm underlying both GRT & QM, which assume that the universe was created (or “caused”) by an initial “Big-Bang” nuclear event (and is expanding due to a purely hypothetical “dark-matter” concept which could not be verified experimentally and which is negated by the New empirically validated “G-D's Physics” Scientific Paradigm, it is necessary to “retrace” the emergence of the basic “Paradigmatic-Crisis”, e.g., signifying this Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm: indicated by the fundamental “theoretical-inconsistency” between GRT & QM, and its principle inability to explain the empirically observed accelerated rate of the universe's expansion – assumed to be “caused” by the (purely hypothetical) “dark-matter” concept (assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe, but which could not be verified experimentally despite numerous attempts to do so over the past two full decades!)) As we've seen, such a (fundamental) “Paradigmatic-Crisis” characterizes (according to Thomas Kuhn's 1962 famous analysis of the “Structure of Scientific Revolutions”) the need for an ensuing “Paradigmatic-Shift” from this Old “Material-Causal” New “G-D's Physics” (CUFT) Scientific Paradigm! Indeed, the acceptance of the New “A-Causal Computation” “G-D's Physics” Scientific Paradigm is dependent upon the fulfillment of few (stringent) criteria including: a) Capacity of the New “G-D's Physics” Scientific Paradigm to resolve the (apparent) GRT-QM “theoretical inconsistency” (which has been shown previously stemming from the discovery of the singular higher-ordered UCP which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels' four basic physical features – at the incredible rate of $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec⁻¹! thereby producing an extremely rapid series of “Universal Frames” comprising the entire physical universe at every “minimal time-point”!) b) Offering an alternative (satisfactory) explanation for the universe's accelerated rate of expansion – based on the UNCIARE's associated CHCF (outlined above); c) Identification- and empirical validation- of at least one unique “Critical Prediction/s” of “G-D's Physics” New Scientific Paradigm as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm's GRT's & QM's predictions! (Indeed, the abovementioned empirical validations of two such unique “Critical Predictions” related to UNCIARE and the “Proton Radius Puzzle” findings indicate that “G-D's Physics” New Scientific Paradigm is more valid than the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm's GRT and QM's corresponding predictions!)

Hence, based upon the fulfillment of these (stringent) necessary conditions for the acceptance of “G-D's Physics” (CUFT) – points at “G-D's Physics” as the New (valid) Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century! It is important to note that this New “G-D's Physics” was shown to resolve the apparent “theoretical-inconsistency” between GRT & QM – and in fact unify between them based on its discovery of the (novel) “Universal Computational Formula”, which was also shown to unify (for the first time in Theoretical Physics) between the Four basic Physical Features (of “space”, “energy”, “mass” and “time”), as well as between the Four Forces! Nevertheless, the New “G-D's Physics” Scientific Paradigm was characterized as an “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm, stemming from its discovery of the singular (higher-ordered) UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s) and the complete “dissolution” of the entire physical universe “in-between” any two consecutive UF's frames (back into the singularity of the UCP)! According to this New “G-D's Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm, there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different- UF's frame/s! This profound new discovery made by the New “G-D's Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm principally negates some of the most basic assumptions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm, including: GRT's “Big-Bang Model” and the existence of any purely hypothetical “dark-matter” concept (as the assumed “caused” for the accelerated expansion of the physical universe, as explained above).

Instead, "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" (empirically validated) Scientific Paradigm points at the fact that the whole origination-sustenance- "dissolution"- and development of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as its entirety) has been "pre-planned" by this singular higher-ordered UCP to evolve the universe from its initial "inanimate matter" through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State" in which Humanity and Science will recognize the singularity of this "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) or "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR), which is also characterized by Humanity's (and Science's) "embracing" of this singular UCP's/UCR's intrinsic properties of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" & "Harmony"! Thus, the New (empirically validated) "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm explains the whole origination- sustenance- ("dissolution"-) and development- of the entire physical universe: not as created by an initial "random" "Big-Bang" nuclear event, and the whole development of the universe – as leading to an ("inevitable") "dissipation" (e.g., based on the Second Law of Thermodynamics, which was shown to be negated by "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm and its CDP); but rather as being "pre-planned" by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR for the fulfillment of the universe's "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State" (e.g., Morally, Spiritually and even Physically)! In that sense, the (above) empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" two (unique) "Critical Predictions"

H. "G-D's Physics New Understanding of the Origination, Sustenance, Development & "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" of the Universe!

Hence, the alternative theoretical explanation offered by "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm for the origination- sustenance- evolution- and indeed the "Ultimate Goal" of the entire physical universe's development is given through "G-D's Physics" newly discovered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP or UCR), and its associated THCD-UCF! Perhaps another "Solomon's Temple Blueprint Plan" Metaphor may be helpful, in order to illustrate the (possible) manner according to which this singular (higher-ordered) UCR has "preplanned" the entire origination- sustenance- and evolution- of the entire physical universe: from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings – towards the fulfillment of the "Perfected Ultimate Geulah Goal", in which Science and Humanity (more generally) will recognize the singularity of this UCR, e.g., including its intrinsic characteristics of "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"!

According to this "Solomon's Temple Blueprint Plan" Metaphor, King Solomon had to "preplan" the whole design and build-up of the (immaculate) Temple from its "Completed-Perfected-Final" stage – "backwards" towards the initial stages of its construction, so that this "Blueprint Plan" will lead up to this "Completed-Perfected-Final" state of the Temple! (We could not imagine a scenario in which King Solomon's builders begin "constructing" this Immaculate Temple – without such a "perfected Blueprint Plan", i.e., just by "experimenting" with different stones with no "preplanned Blueprint Plan" for its orderly completion!?) Equivalently, "G-D's Physics" New (Twenty-First Century's) "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm postulates that this singular higher-ordered UCR has "preplanned" a "Blueprint Plan" – from the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" "backwards" towards the initial stages of "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings, and up to the "Perfected Geulah State" of the universe in which Humanity (and Science) recognize the singularity of this UCR! Indeed, once we fully realize that there cannot exist any "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any two (consecutive or even non-consecutive UF's frame/s), we come to the inevitable conclusion wherein the entire evolution of the whole universe cannot be "caused" by any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between certain "massive" objects and their (assumed) "curvature" of "Space-Time" (or the corresponding determination of the "travelling pathways" of these "massive"

or other "less-massive" objects as "caused" by this assumed "curved Space-Time" fabric), as GRT postulated! Instead, we realize that according to "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, the whole universe is being continuously "created", "dissolved", "re-created" and "evolved" so many "trillions" of time each second –by this singular UCR! Moreover, we realize that the sole manner in which the entire physical universe evolves, is based on this preplanned "Blueprint Plan" of advancing the universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah-Goal" State! Indeed, we currently stand at a "historic time", e.g., equivalent perhaps to Eddington's empirical validation of Einstein's GRT's "Critical Prediction" of Mercury's "double-valued" perihelion's curvature around the Sun – with the empirical validation of two such (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm, as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's & QM's Models! Moreover, this empirical validation of those two (unique) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm – in fact, point at the attainment of Humanity's (and Science's) "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State! This is because the very definition of this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of Humanity and the Universe is precisely one in which Humanity recognizes the singular reality of this UCR, i.e., underlying (and transcending) the entire physical universe, and being characterized through its basic intrinsic properties of: "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" – which will also characterize ("guide" and "typify") Humanity's newly "Perfected Geulah State"!

We therefore begin realizing that the whole "origination"- "sustenance"- and "development" of the entire physical universe is driven by this singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which has "pre-planned" the whole development of the entire physical universe in order to reach that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" of the universe, in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this UCR, alongside its "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"! We realize that since the UCP is the sole "computationally-invariant" Principle (or "reality") that can "produce"- "sustain"- "dissolve"- or "evolve" any exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, as well as "originate"- "sustain" and "evolve" the entirety of the physical universe! And moreover, since that the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR is continuously "originating"- "evolving"- ("dissolving"-) and "developing" the entire physical universe – is "motivated" by this singular higher-ordered UCP's/UCR's intrinsic "sublime characteristics" of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony", and geared towards fulfilling the Universe's "Ultimate Geulah Perfected Goal" State of the Universe (and of Humanity)! Therefore, we are "astonished" to find out that at every "trillionth-of-trillionth etc." of a second (e.g., " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{17} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ") this UCP computes and evolves every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe – including all human-beings, animals, plants and even "inanimate matter" based upon the UCP's THCD's (and associated THCD's-UCF!) which is "steering" the universe (and Humanity) towards that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State, in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this UCP/UCR and begin living in accordance with this UCP's/UCR's "sublime" characteristics of "Morality", "All-Goodness", "Peace" and "Harmony"!

The important point to be noted (here) is that we begin noticing that the manner in which this UCP computes- sustains- ("dissolves"-) and evolves- every exhaustive spatial pixel (as well as the entirety of the whole universe) relies upon its THCD's extremely rapid computation, e.g., at the rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{17} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ " in which the "Human Collective Consciousness Focus" (as well as the Individual Human Consciousness Moral Choice/s) plays a key central role, alongside this singular higher-ordered UCP's "steering" of Humanity and the Universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State"! This is because, when we closely examine those THCD's we notice two very important elements:

a) The sixth Collective Human Consciousness Focus (CHCF) Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of the Universe's Expansion (NCARUE) at the Jewish Rosh Hashanah (JRH) – determines the universe's increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion, i.e., beginning at each JRH's two days' special time-interval! (This year the UNCIARE-JRH took place during Sep. 16th-17th, 2023, for which there was an urgent Call for Astronomers to validate the increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion beginning in these two days and subsequently, relative to the rate of the universe's expansion prior to these two days' JRH time-interval! Data is still missing regarding this urgent call for Astronomers/Cosmologists to validate this year's Sep. 16-17th UNCIARE.) Nevertheless, one of the two unique "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm – which have been empirically validated as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM is this UNCIARE (JRH) Critical Prediction! As shown above, this "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE (JRH) "Critical Prediction" was validated empirically based on the "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (CAGUARE) which supports "G-D's Physics" annual increase at the JRH's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) two days' time-interval! Indeed, such a CAGUARE cannot be accounted for GRT's "constant-rate" expansion of the universe due to the (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter"/"Dark-Energy" concepts – but precisely confirms "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE "Critical Prediction"! This is because based on "G-D's Physics" CHCF postulate which takes place every consecutive JRH's (two days' time interval and remains constant throughout the whole subsequent Jewish Year) it is expected that the universe's expansion rate will increase "over time", i.e., leading to the observed CAGUARE's UNCIARE-JRH phenomenon!

b) Earth's CHCF "Functional Center" of the Universe – In "Space" & "Time"!?

Indeed, the existence of "Hubbles Law" (HL), e.g., indicating that the rate of the universe's expansion – relative to "Earth's Functional Epicenter" increases as a function of the distance of any give galaxy from "Earth's Functional Epicenter" points at Earth functioning as the "Universe's Functional Epicenter"! Moreover, when we take into consideration the combination of HL's Earth's Functional Center together with the (abovementioned) CAGUARE UNCIARE-JRH we must reach the inevitable conclusion wherein Earth's CHCF stands at the basis of Earth's Functional Center – i.e., both in "space" and "time"! In other words, the clear empirical evidence positioning Earth as the "Functional Center" of the universe, as evidenced by HL & associated CAGUARE UNCIARE-JRH indicate that Earth's CHCF is responsible for Earth's UNCIARE-JRH increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion (e.g., every consecutive Jewish Year), and when taken together with HL indicate that Earth's CHCF serves as the "Functional Center" of the entire physical universe both in "space" and "time"!?

c) The UCP's "Non-Continuous Computation of the Universe" (UCP-NC-CU)!

The next "step" in our new understanding of the fundamental "metamorphosis" that "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm creates in our basic understanding of the true "origin", "sustenance" and "development" of the entire physical universe is associated with "G-D's Physics" other unique "Critical Prediction" validation, e.g., associated with the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings! According to "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm, the UCP's computation of the entire physical universe (as well as of any of its multifarious exhaustive spatial pixels) is "non-continuous", i.e., existing only "during" each consecutive UF's frame/s, but "dissolving" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two subsequent UF's frame/s (e.g., therefore the whole physical universe has been redefined as representing only a "computationally-variant" manifestation of the singular "computationally-invariant" UCP which exists "constantly, continuously and uniformly" both "during" its computation of each consecutive UF's

frame/s, and also solely existing without the presence of any physical universe "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s!) Indeed, "G-D's Physics" (second) "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings' unique "Critical Prediction" – differentially predicted this "Proton Radius Puzzle" key findings, wherein the relatively "more massive" Muon particle would be computed by the UCP as more "spatially-consistent" than the relatively "less-massive" electron particle (across a series of UF's frame/s)! This is because according to "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm the UCP's computation of any given particle's "mass" value is based on the UCP's "Object-consistent" computation of each given particle – i.e., with more massive particles being computed as more "spatially-consistent" (as outlined previously) This leads to the UCP's computation of the relatively "more massive" Muon particle as being more "spatially-consistent" than the less-massive electron particle, which then leads to the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings of the relatively "smaller, more accurate measurements" of the Hydrogen's Proton Radius – when encircled by the relatively "more massive" Muon particle, than when encircled by the "standard electron" particle! But, implied within this empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" unique "Proton-Radius Puzzle" "Critical Prediction" is the realization that the UCP's computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as the entire physical universe) – is "non-continuous", i.e., "dissolving" back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Indeed, as indicated above, "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – negates the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in either the "same"- or "different" UF's frame/s, which also implies that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) physical interactions between any two consecutive UF's frame/s!

As shown above, "G-D's Physics" two profound "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" theoretical postulates indicated that the only manner in which the "computationally-variant" universe is "originated", ("dissolved"), sustained and "developed" – at the incredible rate of " $c/2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{-50}$ sec" is based upon the UCP's THCD's-UCF, which has "pre-planned" the whole development of the entire physical universe from its initial "inanimate matter" through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards reaching the universe's "Ultimate Perfected Geulah" State of the universe, in which both Humanity and Science will recognize the singularity of this UCP, alongside its "sublime" characteristics of "Morality", "All-Goodness", "Peace" & "Harmony"!

Since the UCP's "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of the universe relates to Humanity's attainment of such a "Perfected Geulah State", in which all human-beings realize their "oneness" with this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR, i.e., including their realization of the UCP's basic fundamental "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle": which "teaches" every individual human-being to regard any other human-being as "integral inseparable parts" of this same singular higher-ordered UCP, therefore we see that the UCP's execution of every consecutive UF's exhaustive spatial pixels – strongly relates to its computation of each individual human-being's Moral Choice/s at every "minimal time-point", including the (previously delineated) possibility of "Teshuvah" (e.g., corresponding to the UCP's eighth "Teshuva" HCD, which allows every human-being to carry out a sincere "Teshuvah" remorse and conscious decision to not repeat any specific immoral action); which then alters and changes the UCP's computation of the subsequent (ninth) "UCP's Actual Computed Object", (i.e., in terms of "avoiding" and "altering" that individual human-being's next subsequent UF's frame/s presentation of an "equivalent negative situation" in which that individual human-being would have to experience the same "negative immoral situation" which he/she inflicted pain/suffering upon any other individual human-being – since that individual human-being has carried out a genuine "teshuvah" regarding his/her "immoral choice/s")! So,

we can see that at the very center of the UCP's continuous creation- sustenance- and development- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as the entire physical universe's development) stands the UCP's consideration of the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) – at the JRH's two-days' time-interval, which brings about the "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCI-ARE), as well as the UCP's Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle which affects that UCP's computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel (in any subsequent UF's frame/s of the universe), and advances the whole of Humanity towards that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of Humanity and the Universe!

A "Geulah-Driven" Space-Time Evolution of the Universe!

Hence, the alternative theoretical explanation offered by "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm for the origination- sustenance- evolution- and indeed the "Ultimate Goal" of the entire physical universe's development is given through "G-D's Physics" newly discovered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP or UCR), and its associated THCD-UCF! Perhaps another "Solomon's Temple Blueprint Plan" Metaphor may be helpful, in order to illustrate the (possible) manner according to which this singular (higher-ordered) UCR has "preplanned" the entire origination- sustenance- and evolution- of the entire physical universe: from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings – towards the fulfillment of the "Perfected Ultimate Geulah Goal", in which Science and Humanity (more generally) will recognize the singularity of this UCR, e.g., including its intrinsic characteristics of "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"!

According to this "Solomon's Temple Blueprint Plan" Metaphor, King Solomon had to "preplan" the whole design and build-up of the (immaculate) Temple from its "Completed-Perfected-Final" stage – "backwards" towards the initial stages of its construction, so that this "Blueprint Plan" will lead up to this "Completed-Perfected-Final" state of the Temple! (We could not imagine a scenario in which King Solomon's builders begin "constructing" this Immaculate Temple – without such a "perfected Blueprint Plan", i.e., just by "experimenting" with different stones with no "preplanned Blueprint Plan" for its orderly completion?!) Equivalently, "G-D's Physics" New (Twenty-First Century's) "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm postulates that this singular higher-ordered UCR has "preplanned" a "Blueprint Plan" – from the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" "backwards" towards the initial stages of "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings, and up to the "Perfected Geulah State" of the universe in which Humanity (and Science) recognize the singularity of this UCR! Indeed, once we fully realize that there cannot exist any "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any two (consecutive or even non-consecutive UF's frame/s), we come to the inevitable conclusion wherein the entire evolution of the whole universe cannot be "caused" by any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between certain "massive" objects and their (assumed) "curvature" of "Space-Time" (or the corresponding determination of the "travelling pathways" of these "massive" or other "less-massive" objects as "caused" by this assumed "curved Space-Time" fabric), as GRT postulated! Instead, we realize that according to "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, the whole universe is being continuously "created", "dissolved", "re-created" and "evolved" so many "trillions" of time each second – by this singular UCR! Moreover, we realize that the sole manner in which the entire physical universe evolves, is based on this preplanned "Blueprint Plan" of advancing the universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah-Goal" State! Indeed, we currently stand at a "historic time", e.g., equivalent perhaps to Eddington's empirical validation of Einstein's GRT's "Critical Prediction" of Mercury's "double-valued" perihelion's curvature around the Sun – with the empirical validation of two such (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm, as more valid than the

corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's & QM's Models! Moreover, this empirical validation of those two (unique) "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm – in fact, point at the attainment of Humanity's (and Science's) "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State! This is because the very definition of this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State of Humanity and the Universe is precisely one in which Humanity recognizes the singular reality of this UCR, i.e., underlying (and transcending) the entire physical universe, and being characterized through its basic intrinsic properties of: "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" – which will also characterize ("guide" and "typify") Humanity's newly "Perfected Geulah State"!

Intriguingly, based on the discovery of these THCD's characteristics of the operation of this singular higher-ordered UCR (and associated THCD's-UCF), we realize that the whole "origination", "sustenance", and "development" of the entire physical universe has been "preplanned" by this singular higher-ordered UCR in order to advance the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter form through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the Ultimate "Geulah Perfected Goal" state of the universe, in which Science and Humanity (more generally) will recognize the singularity of this UCR, and its THCD's ("sublime") characteristics including: "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" – which will therefore also typify Humanity's Perfected "Geulah Goal" State (behavior and attitude towards each other etc.)! According to this New "G-D's Physics" THCD's Geulah-Goal Directed Universe's theoretical perspective, the universe was not created (or "caused") by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event, nor has its evolution been the result of any ("random": direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels – including its (abovementioned) negation of the (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts, or "Cosmological Constant" etc.; but rather as originating from the UCP's/UCR's "preplanned Blueprint Plan" to develop the universe from its "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings leading up to that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" of Humanity and the universe! In order to perhaps (further) elucidate this novel conception of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, we can utilize the "Cinematic-Film Metaphor" (which has been used previously) to explain this new conception of the universe's development: If we were to imagine a certain "action-film" such as "James Bond's" famous films, we could envision a whole "cascade of events" in which James Bond escapes "grave dangers" in order to protect the "vital interests" of his government (and the whole free world), ultimately leading to the abolishment of the "evil organization" trying to sabotage "world-peace", and fulfillment of such a desired "World-Peace Agreement" that would advance Humanity towards a "cooperative, peaceful and prosperous future"... But, if we analyze (deeper) this Cinematic-Film Metaphor scenario, we could see that the whole progression and "plot" of the film has been "pre-planned" before the "shooting" of the film! In fact, we could not imagine any "occurrence" taking place within the film which would "affect" or "alter" this "pre-planned plot" of the film, nor any "interactions" occurring within the film! On the contrary, we realize that all of these (apparently) "random occurrences" were "pre-planned" by the producer of the film in order to lead us (the "viewers" of the film) to realize a certain "motto" of this ("thrilling") "James Bond Action Film" – i.e., such as: to believe that there is always a "good-ending" in Life, and that "good prevails"! In much the same manner, it is suggested that this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR has "pre-planned" the whole development of the entire physical universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings leading up to the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" of Humanity and the universe, and therefore that the whole "origination", "sustenance" and "development" of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as the entirety of the whole physical universe) develops solely based on this singular higher-ordered UCP's/UCR's (preplanned) "Perfected Geulah Goal Directed Universe" Blueprint Plan!

In other words, we must embrace an entirely new conception of the entire "origination"- "sustenance"- and "development" of the physical universe: which was not created by an initial "random Big-Bang" nuclear event, or that is being expanded (at an accelerated rate) by purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts; Instead the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm explains the whole "origination"- "sustenance" and "development" of the entire physical universe (as well as of every exhaustive spatial pixel comprising it) solely based on the fulfilment of the UCP's/UCR's preplanned "Blueprint Plan" for a "Geulah Perfected Goal Driven Universe"! Therefore, instead of assuming that the universe was created by a random initial ("Big-Bang") nuclear event (which is assumed to have "caused" the creation of all the suns, galaxies, planets, mass and energy in the universe); and moreover (based on this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumed "Darwin's Natural Selection Principle", DNSP – which were all negated by "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" empirically validated Scientific Paradigm) that the various Biological forms' evolution on Earth were also created by "random" "material-causal" physical interactions between certain "genetically-mutated" organisms and a "challenging environment" etc.; the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm stipulates that the whole development of the entire physical universe has been "pre-planned" from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals, and human-beings – all leading to the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" state of Humanity recognizing the singularity of this UCP/UCR and behaving in accordance with this UCP's/UCR's "sublime" characteristics of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony"!

Moreover, based on the direct empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH increase in the rate of the universe's expansion, which is dependent upon the (stipulated) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) (e.g., of Millions of Jews praying and focusing on this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR, i.e., in religious terms: "G-D") therefore, according to the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm it is clear that the increase in the universe's accelerated expansion rate (e.g., manifesting through the otherwise unexplained abovementioned CAGUARE phenomenon) – is contingent upon the existence of such CHCF (UNCAIRE-JRH) every consecutive year, from the very "beginning" of the universe and up till today! In other words, according to the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm the whole evolution and expansion of the entire physical universe – and specifically the (otherwise unexplained CAGUARE phenomenon) critically depends upon the CHCF associated with the JRH's UNCIARE (e.g., empirically validated by "G-D's Physics" Critical UNCIARE prediction above, and urgent call for Astronomers testing of the specific UNCIARE-JRH increase in the universe's expansion accelerated rate during the upcoming JRH on the 16th-17th of Sep., 2023!) *This means that according to the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm's (empirically validated) CHCF, and associated THCD's-UCF (which delineates the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR computes every consecutive UF's frame/s at the unfathomable rate of "c²/h" = 1/36⁻⁵⁰ sec!), it is hereby stipulated that the UCP's/UCR's initial "origination" of the whole universe – including its complete "progression" from "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings took place in only six (or seven) days (i.e., to include the "Ultimate Geulah Goal State")!*

This is because it is only "logical" to assume that if the UCP/UCR simultaneously computes every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s) at the incredible rate of "c²/h" = 1.36-50 (sec!) by employing specifically those seven HCD's which are computing and "materializing" each exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (based on the Three Initial Key HCD's which together comprise the THCD's!); and if indeed (as proven empirically through "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE "Critical Prediction") the continuous increase in the universe's expansion rate critically depended upon the presence of human-beings and their capacity

to carry out this CHCF-JRH for each consecutive years since the UCR's "origination" of the universe (e.g., till the current time); therefore, it is "logical" to assume that the UCR has created the whole universe based on its seven HCD's (e.g., corresponding HCD for each day!)

Plausibility of "G-D's Physics" New "Universe's Seven Days Origination" (USDO) Model

It is important to note (on a philosophical-scientific level) that since the actual capacity of Science (or Physics) to carry out any direct measurement of the "origination" of the universe – is strictly negated by GRT, due to the fact that we cannot move at a speed exceeding the "Speed of Light" (and therefore cannot "move back in time" to directly observe the actual "origination" of the universe!) therefore, we can only "contrast" between different Scientific Paradigms – such as the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (underlying GRT's "Big-Bang" Model) and the New "G-D's Physics", and consequently decide which of these Scientific Paradigms prevails! Significantly, the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm has been proven to be "more valid" than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (underlying both GRT & QM) based on the empirical validation of its two unique "Critical Predictions" – e.g., associated with the "Proton Radius Puzzle" findings and the UNCIARE (JRH)! Hence, the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT's "Big-Bang" Model was negated based on "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, and therefore its THCD's-UCF theoretical explanation of the continuous "origination", "dissolution" "sustenance", and "development" of the entire physical universe – towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" must be accepted, including its corresponding stipulation of the "seven days creation" of the entirety of the universe (e.g., with all "inanimate" and "animate" forms including human-beings!) Indeed, a further (even more direct) empirical validation (previously called for Astronomers to carry out) that would test for the appearance of the relatively "more massive" Muon particle in a greater number of "Fine-Temporal Measurements" (FTM) in a greater number of UF's than the equivalent (negatively charged) electron particle would directly validate the ongoing continuous computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe by this singular higher-ordered UCP, e.g., giving further support for "G-D's Physics" stipulated (novel) "UCP's Severn Day Creation Model" (UCP-SDCM)!

Over and beyond the clear (abovementioned) validation of two unique "Critical Predictions" of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both GRT & QM, which forces Science to accept "G-D's Physics" as the New Twenty-first Century (valid) Scientific Paradigm, there are several further supporting elements taken from "G-D's Physics" "internal-validity" also pointing at the plausibility of its USDO Model of the origination, as part of the basic "Geulah Perfected State Driven Universe" new understanding of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm!

a) It is clear that the universe could not be caused by the initially assumed "Big-Bang" nuclear event, nor could its accelerated rate of expansion could be accounted for by the purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts, nor through Einstein's Equations' three EEE's (as negated by "G-D's Physics" CDP)!

b) Moreover, based on "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" New Scientific Paradigm (as noted above) due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) and the complete "dissolution" of the entire physical universe "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s, we reached the inevitable conclusion that the universe cannot evolve based on any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (existing in the "same" or "different" UF's frame/s), and therefore that the only "viable means" for explaining the origination- sustenance- "dissolution"- re-computation- and development of the entire physical universe (or of any of its multifarious exhaustive spatial pixels) can only

be given based on the analysis of the singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR that is continuously "originating" – "dissolving" "re-creating" and "evolving" every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec⁻¹)

c) The complete "dependence" – and in fact "inseparability" of the entire physical universe from this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR is significantly strengthened based on the (abovementioned) profound "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" theoretical postulates – which indicates that there exist only this one singular reality, which is this "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR or UCP) that exists both "during" its (simultaneous) computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s, and also solely exists (without the presence of any physical universe) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Indeed, according to these two (profound) theoretical postulates the entire physical universe (and all of its exhaustive spatial pixels) does not exist "independently" of this singular UCR – but rather merely represents a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of this singular UCR reality!

d) Hence, we realize that the whole existence- (continuous) origination-sustenance- and development- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe totally depends upon the "intrinsic characteristics" of this singular UCR/UCP, which were discovered as the UCP's "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" (THCD's), alongside the UCP THCD's Universal Computational Formula: as noted above (and previously), these UCP's THCD's and (associated) UCF – all point at "G-D's Physics" "Geulah Driven Universe"! In other words, these UCP's THCD's point at the UCP's "Pre-planned Blueprint Plan" for advancing the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings leading to the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" state of Humanity and the universe!

e) Indeed, according to "G-D's Physics" "Reversed Time Geulah Goal" postulate, the whole "origination" - "sustenance" - and "development" of the entire physical universe has been "pre-planned" by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR from its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" State in which Humanity (and Science) recognize the singularity of this UCP/UCR and its "sublime" characteristics (e.g., THCD's) specifically leading to the universe's "Ultimate Geulah Perfected State" of "Peace", "Harmony", "Morality" and "All-Goodness" (which will therefore also characterize Humanity's Geulah State and accompanying behavior!)

f) When taken together with the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) "Critical Prediction" increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion stipulated to occur during the two days' Jewish "Rosh Hashanah" (New Year) "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) – which was empirically supported based on the observed (and otherwise "unexplained" "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" [CAGUARE]); and more specifically, the current call for Astronomers & Cosmologists to empirically validate a more direct "Critical Prediction" of "G-D's Physics" regarding the UNCIARE's increased rate of the universe's expansion predicted to take place during the upcoming JRH on Sep. 16th & 17th, 2023 (e.g., relative to prior to Sep 16th-17th, and carry over in an increased universe's accelerated rate of expansion throughout the whole subsequent Jewish Year!) These results clearly indicate that the empirically validate CAGUARE (supporting "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE "Critical Prediction", as explained above and previously) supports "G-D's Physics" centrality of the CHCF as key in explaining the UNCIARE increase in the universe's rate of expansion over the course of the universe's development course (rather than "G-D's Physics" negated purely hypothetical "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" or any of Einstein's other tree EEE's, as described above)!

g) This means that presence of such a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF) must have existed from the initial "origination" of the universe by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR! Specifically, when taken together with the UNCIARE-JRH indication that this empirically validated UNCIARE may take place during the JRH's two days' time interval then this implies that from the "first year" of the universe's "origination" by the UCP/UCR, there must have existed this UNCIARE-JRH's CHCF that allowed the (initial) "accelerated expansion rate of the universe! This implies that from the universe's "origination point" by the UCP, shortly after its initial origination, there must have occurred this CHCF JRH UNCIARE phenomenon!

h) When taken together with "G-D's Physics" THCD's UCF (precise) description of the manner in which the UCP accurately computes each subsequent UF's (e.g., at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec⁻¹) based primarily upon the UCP's (consecutive) computation of the "seven secondary HCD's" (as "preplanned" and "executed" by the UCP's Three Key Initial HCD's Blueprint Plan for steering the universe from its inanimate through animate: plants, animals and human-beings towards that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State") – then this suggests as "plausible" and "reasonable" that the UCP's initial "origination" of the entire physical universe – from its initial "inanimate" state through its pre-planned subsequent "animate": plants, animals and human-beings (and even perhaps initial recognition by a human-being of the singularity of this UCP, i.e., "G-D" Presence) may have occurred during the first seven days – one day for each of these secondary seven HCD's! Subsequently, after this "first week" in which all "animate" and "animate" (plants, animals and human-beings) have been "originated" by the UCP/UCR, it is suggested that the first CHCF JRH-UNCIARE occurred which allowed for the UCP's first UNCIARE-JRH increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion!

Hence, it's become clear that Science (and Humanity) have now reached a "critical turning point" in its development: instead of Science's "lifelong" basic "Material-Causal" assumption (e.g., including even "Newtonian Classical Mechanics") wherein it was assumed that everything in the universe can be explained as being "caused" by a certain "material-causal" (direct or indirect) physical interactions between any given (finite) number of material elements!? Such as GRT's basic assumption, wherein the origination of the entire physical universe was "caused" by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event, or the expansion of the universe is "caused" by the purely hypothetical "Dark Matter" or "Dark-Energy" concepts? Or such as QM's assumed determination of any given subatomic particle or wave entity based on the direct physical interaction/s of a given subatomic "probe" element with a corresponding subatomic "target's probability wave-function", which "causes" this (assumed) "target's probability wave function" to "collapse" into a single "complimentary" "space-energy" or "mass-time" value? The New empirically validated "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm completely negated such basic "Material-Causal" assumption – e.g., due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any single- or multiple- UF's frame/s, and the complete "dissolution" of all such exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Therefore, the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm advanced our new (higher) understanding wherein the only manner in which this singular (higher-ordered) "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) continuously "originates", "sustains", ("dissolves") and "develops" the entire physical universe is based upon its "pre-planned" Blueprint Plan of "steering" the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" state of the entire physical universe in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this UCP as the sole reality behind the universe (e.g., and also transcending its existence); which will also include Humanity's recognition of this singular higher-ordered UCR's "sublime" characteristics

of "Morality", "All-Goodness", "Peace" & "Harmony" which will therefore also characterize Humanity's "peaceful", "meaningful" and "harmonious" ("goodwill") existence!

The "robustness" of any given Scientific Theory, i.e., and especially the discovery and empirical validation of a New Scientific Paradigm (NSP) in any given discipline – far exceeds its ability (merely) to satisfy the necessary (stringent) criteria to accept this NSP, as more "valid" (and "satisfactory") than the Old Paradigm! As mentioned earlier, according to Thomas Kuhn's (1962) famous (and well-accepted) analysis of the "Structure of Scientific Revolutions", the appearance of a "New Scientific Paradigm" (NSP) ensues the existence of basic fundamental "Paradigmatic-Crisis" of the "Old Paradigm" – in our case this is the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying both GRT & QM, characterized by an apparent basic "theoretical inconsistency" between GRT & QM, and this Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's inability to account for the accelerated expansion of the physical universe, e.g., assumed to be "caused" by (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter" and "Dark-Energy" which are supposed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass and energy in the universe, but which could not be detected or verified experimentally (despite two full decades of trying to do so?!)

Earth's Functional Epicenter of the Universe: G-D's Physics' Fulfillment of the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" of Humanity!

We therefore (indeed) reach a major "pivotal turning-point" along the development of Science – with the acceptance of "G-D's Physics" as the New (satisfactory) Twenty-First Century Physics Scientific Paradigm (e.g., based upon the clear empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" two unique "Critical Predictions" as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT & QM)! As we've seen, the acceptance of "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm brings with it a whole revision of some of our most basic (and fundamental prior) "material-causal" (key) assumptions, such as the "Big-Bang" Model (as a part of GRT's Einstein's Equations) which assumed that the whole universe was created (or "caused") by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event which produced (or "caused") all of the "suns", "galaxies", "mass" and "energy" in the universe – that was strictly negated based on "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" (e.g., indicating that there could not have existed any direct or indirect "material-causal" physical relationships between any two or more exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe due to the UCP's "simultaneous" computation of all such exhaustive spatial pixels comprising every consecutive UF's frame/s, and the complete "dissolution" of the entire physical universe back into the singularity of this UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s!?) More generally, GRT assumes that the whole (continuous) evolution of the entire physical universe is "caused" by direct "material-causal" physical relationship/s that exist between certain "massive objects" and their "curvature of Space-Time" (or between this "curved Space-Time" and its determination of the "travelling pathway/s" of these "massive" or other "less-massive objects), and that the "accelerated expansion" of the universe is caused by (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" (DM/DE) based on their interaction with certain "galactic elements" at the farthest regions of the universe – which were all negated based on the UCP's "simultaneous" computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (for every consecutive UF's frame/s), and the complete "dissolution" of the entire physical universe "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s! Likewise (as shown above and previously) this New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm also negated the basic "material-causal" assumption which also underlies QM's explanation of the assumed direct "material-causal" physical interaction that exists between the subatomic "probe" element and the corresponding subatomic "target's probability wave-function" that "causes" the "collapse" of the subatomic "target's probability wave-function" into a single (complimentary: "space-energy" or "mass-time" value)!

Instead, "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm points at the existence of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (e.g., at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 50 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ") thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every "minimal time-point"... Indeed, this profound new insight into the manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCP is able to compute the Four basic Physical features (e.g., of "space" and "energy", or "mass" and "time") based on the UCP (two out of three) "Computational Dimensions" (i.e., "Framework" & "Consistency") as the four possible combinations of these two UCP's Computational Dimensions – simultaneously for all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s at the "unfathomable" rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 50 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ") was also shown to unify – for the first time in Physics, between those four basic Physical Features (as well as between the Four Forces of Nature) within the singular "Universal Computational Formula"!

Even beyond that, "G-D's Physics" two (profound) "Computational Invariance Principle" and associated "Universal Consciousness Reality" completely alter our basic understanding of the entire physical universe – which ceases to exist as an "independent" "constant" and "continuous" reality, but is rather seen as a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of this singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which exists continuously both "during" its (simultaneous) computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising each consecutive UF's frame/s (e.g., at the "unfathomable" rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 50 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ") and also solely exists (without the presence of any physical universe) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Indeed, the recognition of the singularity of this "Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR) which solely comprises the "true-consistent" reality underlying (and "transcending") the entire physical universe has led to focusing on a better understanding of this singular UCP's/UCR's "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" (THCD's), and more generally – the UCP's/UCR's "Pre-planned Blueprint Plan" for attainment of the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of the universe (and of Humanity) in which Science and Humanity will recognize the singularity of this higher-ordered UCP/UCR, alongside a recognition of its "sublime" characteristics of: "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony" (which will therefore also characterize Humanity's behavior and existence!)

Indeed, "G-D's Physics" postulate of the "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal Hypothesis" suggests that the UCP has "pre-planned" the whole development of universe from its initial "matter" through "inanimate": plants, animals, human-beings and up to that "Ultimate Geulah Goal State" of Humanity (as mentioned above and previously). It should be noted that since according to "G-D's Physics" New (empirically validated) Scientific Paradigm, the whole "purpose" and "Ultimate Goal" of the development of the entire physical universe – from its initial "inanimate matter" through "animate: plants, animals and human-beings" etc. is only in order to advance Humanity towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State", and since according to "G-D's Physics" analysis of the "Three Initial Key" (TIK) "Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" (previously delineated) the "first" Wisdom/Free-Will חכמה of the UCP is its wish to create an apparently "independent-material world" (e.g., which seems "independent" of the singular UCR "true reality") – which will be (nevertheless) "steered" by this singular UCP towards fulfilling that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of Humanity and the universe; with the two other KIT HCD's also continuously computing, advancing and "adjusting" every consecutive UF's frame/s and every individual human-being towards fulfilling this Ultimate Perfected Geulah State of Humanity (and the Universe)! Alongside the two other KIT's of the "Conscious-Moral Development (CMD) Computation" HCD – which has planned the whole "Conscious-Moral Development" of the whole universe, i.e., from "inanimate matter" through "animate": plants,

animals and human-beings up to the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of Humanity, and the actual "Consistency" HCD's execution of the four different facets of: a) "Geulah-Driven Development" (GDD), wherein every consecutive UF's frame/s is geared towards advancing the Universe (and Humanity) towards that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal" b) CMD-actual execution. c) "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" (DEMP). d) Gimatria computation – the basic "building-blocks" of all "inanimate" and "animate" objects in the universe.

We therefore see that the whole "origination"- "sustenance"- and "development"- of the entire physical universe has been "pre-planned" in order to develop the universe from its initial "inanimate" matter through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings, all intended to attain the universe's "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of Humanity and the universe! So, the "centrality of Human Consciousness" becomes "crystal clear" – within the context of the New "G-D's Physics" conceptual model, which places the emphasis on the UCP's/UCR's "aim" of "driving" the whole development of the entire physical universe towards Humanity's attainment of that "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State", in which all of Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this higher-ordered UCP/UCR (and its "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony")! This centrality of Human Consciousness in this New "G-D's Physics" (21st Century) Scientific Paradigm has also been proven (empirically) through "G-D's Physics" unique (abovementioned) "UNCIARE-JRH" results: indicating that in contrast to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's (purely hypothetical) DM/DE concepts which assume that the universe's rate of expansion should remain "constant" across time, "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH "Critical Prediction" predicted that due to the "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (CHCF), in which Millions of Jew focus (solely) on this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP/UCR) during the two days' (special) "time-interval" of the "Jewish Rosh-Hashanah", therefore there should occur an "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE-JRH, which this year occurred during Sep. 16-17th, 2023) – relative to the rate of the universe's expansion rate prior to Sep. 16-17th (which should continue throughout the whole subsequent Jewish Year); which should amount to an increase in the universe's rate of expansion over time! Therefore, the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH "Critical Prediction" through the otherwise unexplained "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (CAGUARE) – differentially supported "G-D's Physics" UNCIARE-JRH Critical Prediction (but could not be explained by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's purely hypothetical DM/DE assumed "constant" rate of the universe's expansion). More specifically, this unequivocal support of "G-D's Physics" (unique) UNCIARE-JRH "Critical Prediction" highlights (once again) the centrality of Human Consciousness – because it indicates that the abovementioned (otherwise "unexplained" CAGUARE phenomenon) can be accounted for based on the centrality of this CHCF demonstrated through the UNCIARE-JRH (confirmed) increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion!

Hence, the centrality of this CHCF has been demonstrated as the "Functional Epicenter" of the universe through the UNCIARE-JRH "in time", i.e., specifically occurring during the two days' time interval of the JRH (every year)! Indeed, it is this centrality of the CHCF (e.g., "in time") – which was previously (and above) shown to "challenge" and "alter" the (assumed) "time-scaling" of the universe; which is due to the centrality of the CHCF "during" the sixth day of creation which was necessary in order to begin this "UNCIARE-JRH" gradual increase in the universe's accelerated rate of expansion over time! Moreover, the centrality of this CHCF (e.g., together with this CHCF's Earth localization) – as the "Functional Epicenter" of the universe also "in space", based on the well-known "Hubble's constant" indicating that the rate of the farthest regions of the universe – relative to Earth are accelerating at a higher rate than the "closer regions"

of the universe to Earth!? Consequently, "G-D's Physics" associates this "Hubble's constant" (e.g., largely "unexplained" phenomenon) with "centrality of the "CHCF's Earth's Functional Epicenter", "in space"! Indeed, we can see the centrality of the CHCF and its associated Earth localization as the fulfilment of the UCP's pre-planned "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State" of Humanity – signaled by Science's "crowning" of "G-D's Physics" as the New Twenty-First Century Physics Paradigm!

Dedication

This profound article is dedicated to the Lubavitcher Rabbi, Maimonides, the Rashbi, and also to my (diseased) mother, Dr. Tirza Bentwich, my Beloved wife, Shulamit Bentovish, and beloved children: Shoham, Nethanel-Yossef and Neomy Tirzah Shulamit Bentwich! May you all grow in a Newly transformed World of "G-D's Physics" accepted beginning of Humanity's "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State", in which the whole of Humanity will recognize our "oneness" and "inseparability" from that singular higher "Universal Consciousness Reality" ("UCR" or "G-D") and hence, lead a life characterized by the UCR's "sublime characteristics" of "All-Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" & "Harmony"!

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